

Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg
Faculty of Natural Sciences II
Institute for Mathematics

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Theoretical Approaches to Integrated Information and Complexity

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Author: Carlotta Langer

Hr. Dr. Löbus
Martin-Luther-Universität
Halle-Wittenberg

Prof. Dr. Ay
Max Planck Institute for
Mathematics in the Sciences

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1 Introduction

My master thesis discusses the currently developing field of complexity measures belonging to the theory of integrated information. Introductions to the concepts of complexity and integrated information are given in the next two sections. The theory of integrated information has become well known and evolved through different versions in the last years. This is why section 1.2 provides a brief overview of the developments in this area. Additionally, section 1.3 includes a short definition of the systems we are interested in, so that the reader might be able to keep the goal in mind during the theoretical foundations in the second section.

These foundations consist of four different parts, namely information theory, information geometry, graphical models and conditional independence statements. The last two can be seen in the context of information geometry, but have also strong connections to other fields and are therefore independent subsections. Graphical models will be a useful tool to understand the concepts of the different measures, and conditional independence statements are very important in the context of the measure called integrated information.

The main part of this thesis is the third section about different complexity measures. Using the framework for defining complexity measures, developed in the second section, leads to the discussion of five different ones that were already introduced and compared in [37] and [30]. There exist other proposed measures, but the presented ones are well known and linked in the following sense:

The concept of mutual information does not lead to a valid measure, but can be seen as an upper bound for complexity measures. The sum of transfer entropies is a natural arising idea in this context. Unfortunately it does exceed the upper bound set by mutual

information already in very simple settings. Stochastic interaction was introduced by Ay in [6]. It has useful properties and satisfies another requirement, Postulate 1, but it also can exceed the mutual information. Geometric integrated information proposed by Amari in [2] is bounded from above by the mutual information, but does not hold Postulate 1.

As a solution Amari, Tsuchiya and Oizumi proposed in [5] a measure called integrated information. This measure satisfies the demanded properties, but is not analytically calculable in general. To get a better understanding of this type of measure we analyze in section 3.6 the structure of the families of distributions belonging to it and present a new divergence that satisfies a generalized Pythagorean theorem. Applying the idea of iterative scaling presented in section 3.4.1 leads to the definition of a new algorithm. In section 1.2 we evaluate its properties but unfortunately it does not converge towards the distribution needed in order to calculate the integrated information measure. The relations are displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Connection between the different presented measures.

Additionally, a new approach to a measure is proposed in section 3.5 that attempts to solve the problem of stochastic interaction by introducing a common exterior influence. This measure satisfies Postulate 1, but still needs further investigations in order to determine whether it also satisfies Postulate 2.

The last discussed measure is the TSE-complexity, which does not necessarily fit into the framework of the other measures, but can be seen as a starting point of complexity measures in the context of integrated information.

1.1 Complexity

There are many different ways to approach the concept of complexity. The one presented here is sometimes related to the following quote:

“Since that which is compounded out of something so that the whole is one, not like a heap but like a syllable-now the syllable is not its elements, ba is not the same as b and a [...]” -Aristotle¹.

This can be abbreviated to “The whole is more than the sum of its parts”. Using this understanding of complexity the method we will use is to first divide the system in question into parts. Then we calculate the difference between the whole one and the partial system. Depending on the magnitude of the difference we will call a system more or less complex. This means that a system that behaves the same way, before and after dividing it, originally consisted of parts and is therefore exactly the sum of them. We will define the considered systems in section 1.3 formally and motivate them by introducing the concept of information integration in the next section.

Aside from the concept above, one could also ask the question of the minimal effort one has to make to describe or generate an object or system. This is the notion of complexity described in [34]. There exists a broad spectrum of complexity concepts relating to this approach, which differ for instance in the degree to which a system has to be described in order to be considered fully determined. One could take a system as fully determined if it is completely generated or one could also see a characterization as sufficient.

Corresponding to this idea the complexity theory in computer science quantifies the complexity of problems via memory space and computation time. In it they determine the minimally needed amount of space and time to solve the problems on formal machines such as register machines.

In this thesis we will use the concept of complexity as something that is more than the sum of its parts. A geometric approach to this can be found in section 6.1.1 in [7].

¹[4] in *Metaphysics*, Vol. VII, 17

1.2 Integrated Information

Tononi, Sporns and Edelman published in 1994 the article “A measure for brain complexity: Relating functional segregation and integration in the nervous system” [53]. They describe the idea of their measure in the discussion of this paper as

“roughly speaking, how much more integrated the whole is than its parts ”.

This understanding of complexity clearly belongs to the one described in the previous section. Starting here it evolved into a broad theory that investigates the origins of consciousness. Fully describing every aspect of it is not within the scope of this thesis, but the following paragraphs will present the milestones in the development of this theory in order to be able to locate the complexity measures discussed in this thesis in the spectrum of integrated information theory.

The initial idea of Tononi et al. is to combine two seemingly opposing views in neuroscience, namely the localizationist and the holistic approach. The first approach focuses on the modularity of the brain while the second one emphasizes the global functions. Hence they propose a framework in which they analyse the dependence characteristics of groups of neurons with increasing size, capturing the modularity by grouping the neurons and including the holistic approach by treating more and more groups till eventually the whole system is considered. They do so by using information theoretic concepts like entropy and mutual information. Then they estimate the average integration over subgroups of neurons of increasing size. The result is a complexity measure that will be discussed in section 3.7. In order to be able to define this measure they make the assumptions that statical properties do not change over time, therefore they use a stationary stochastic process to model it, that the anatomical connectivity is fixed and that there is no input from the environment.

A more detailed description of the concept of this measure, its implications regarding the brain functions and suggestions for experimental testing was published in [51] in 1998.

In [53] the concept of consciousness plays only a minor role and in [51] it is not mentioned at all. But for example the paper “Consciousness and Complexity” [50] from 1999 contains a formulation of the goal to characterize the kind of processes a group of neurons must have in order to be able to constitute to conscious experience. Two core properties are identified in [50], the first one is a large amount of possible different states the physical system can be in and the second one is a high functionally integrated structure. The last part means that it cannot be divided in smaller structures without loss of functionality. Consideration of different neurological and neurophysiological theories and data sets leads them to the following dynamic core hypothesis:

“1) A group of neurons can contribute directly to conscious experience only if it is part of a distributed functional cluster that achieves high integration in hundreds of milliseconds.

2) To sustain conscious experience, it is essential that this functional cluster be highly differentiated, as indicated by high values of complexity.”

A large group of neurons satisfying the properties above are called a dynamic core.

The focus then shifts with [52] published in 2003 to measuring integrated information. As pointed out in [52] the neural complexity measure introduced in [53] does only capture the average integrated information and does not reflect whether the system consists of independent integrated subsets or one entity. To resolve this, they define the index of functional clustering (CI) that compares the dependence within the subset to the dependence between this subset and the rest of the system. Unfortunately it does not differentiate between causal connections or mere correlations. Additionally, the symbol Φ gets introduced for integrated information, where the I stands for the information and the O for the system it is integrated in.

The concept of integrated information was introduced by Tononi in [48] in 2004 more clearly. He distinguishes the key properties that determine consciousness mentioned above, namely information and integration, and highlights the importance of the integration of information with the help of an easy thought experiment. Consider on the one hand a high resolution camera taking a picture and on the other hand a human looking at the same scene. Of course the camera has many different states in which the photodiodes can be in, but they do not interact with each other. We would not call a camera conscious and the difference he highlights is that the information gets integrated inside the brain and stays separate inside the camera.

This theory states that a system should be able to generate consciousness if it has a large number of different states and can not be divided in causally independent subsystems. The functional clusters mentioned earlier are now called complexes. He backs his theory up by comparing it to the function of the brain, in which some regions are also more associated with consciousness than others. Later this has been studied by using data from EEG scans during wakefulness and different states of sleeping in [13] in 2013.

A summary of his theory can be found in “Consciousness as Integrated Information: a Provisional Manifesto” [49]. In the section “A Mathematical Analysis: Quantifying Integrated Information” he describes the method, which will be used in this thesis, that is using the KL-divergence to measure the difference between the full probability distribution and the one consisting of parts. He uses a decomposition called MIP (minimal information principle) that divides a system into minimal parts.

In [8] this theory gets extended from stationary stochastic processes to discrete dynamical systems. The systems there are modeled by a Markov-process on discrete timesteps. This is the framework we will introduce in the next section. The measure for integrated information presented in [8] is discussed and generalized in [9] by Barrett and Seth, which results in a measure that behaves very similar to the stochastic interaction introduced by Ay in [6]. We will see different measures belonging to this context and their connection in section 3. Comparisons of those are [37] and [30].

Different integrated information measures proposed by Tononi get tested in [26] in the context of an artificial agent learning to perform a task. They conclude that the integrated information increases along with the fitness of the agent.

An updated version of the integrated information theory can be found in [47] and [35]. The latter is called “From the Phenomenology to the Mechanisms of Consciousness: Integrated Information Theory 3.0” and includes five axioms. The axioms are:

- *Existence*: consciousness as an undeniable aspect of reality.
- *Composition*: consciousness is structured into different aspects, like observing shapes and colours.
- *Information*: consciousness is informative, meaning that an experience differs from a huge number of other experiences.
- *Integration*: consciousness is integrated so that each component can not be reduced into independent components.
- *Exclusion*: consciousness is exclusive in the sense that one experience excludes others.

Claiming that this theory determines consciousness is highly controversial, the following cited critical views do not represent the entire existing range, but should provide examples of controversial points.

The axioms above are individually examined in the opinion paper [10] and Bayne concludes that the axioms fail their purpose. Cerullo discusses in [14] mainly the fifth axiom “exclusion” and discards it as not self-evident. Aaronson criticises in his blog post [1] the problematic definition of the MIP measure and he considers the theory to be a necessary condition for consciousness, not a sufficient one. Pautz asks in [39] what exactly a certain amount of consciousness is.

Whether or not this theory really leads to the assessment of consciousness is highly debatable, but it seems to be a promising approach to investigate neural systems. In my opinion the existence of such a variety of different measures for Φ alone shows that this should be handled as a work in progress rather than a completed field. Additionally the close connection to information theory and information geometry makes it possible to analyse the proposed methods mathematically.

1.3 Systems

Following the concept of integrated information described in the previous section, the systems mentioned above can be networks of interactions between, for example, probability distributions, stochastic processes or dynamical systems. Here we model these systems as Markov process similar to the framework introduced in [8].

Let $(Z_t)_{t \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a stationary, discrete, n -dimensional Markov-process with

$$(Z_t) := (Z_{1,t}, \dots, Z_{n,t}). \quad (1)$$

We consider a stochastic process to be a Markov-process if the following definition holds.

Definition 1 (Discrete Markov-process). A discrete Markov-process is a sequence of random vectors $(Z_t)_{t \in \mathbb{N}}$ with probability distribution P and the property that its conditional probability only depends on the previous time step:

$$P(Z_{t+1} \mid Z_1, \dots, Z_t) = P(Z_{t+1} \mid Z_t).$$

A discrete stochastic process is stationary, if it does not change when shifted in time:

$$P(Z_{1,t}, \dots, Z_{n,t}) = P(Z_{1,t+\tau}, \dots, Z_{n,t+\tau}), \quad \tau \in \mathbb{N}.$$

As described in section 1.2, we are able to assume this stochastic process is a stationary Markov-process. Now we take a look at the transition between t and $t + 1$. Considering Definition 2 we see, that it is sufficient to only discuss one time step. This is the reason why we will rename the random vectors

$$\begin{aligned} X &= (X_1, \dots, X_n) := (Z_{1,t}, \dots, Z_{n,t}) \\ Y &= (Y_1, \dots, Y_n) := (Z_{1,t+1}, \dots, Z_{n,t+1}) \end{aligned}$$

The random vector $Z = (X, Y)$ takes values in $\mathcal{Z} = \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}$.

Additionally, we denote by $\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$ the set of functions from \mathcal{Z} to \mathbb{R} and by $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$ the set of probability distributions on \mathcal{Z}

$$\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) := \left\{ P \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}} \mid P(z) \geq 0 \ \forall z \in \mathcal{Z}, \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) = 1 \right\}.$$

The probability distribution $P(X, Y) \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$ contains the whole information of the system. In order to determine the complexity we will compare this probability distribution

to one that assumes that we have only a part of the interactions. We will take a closer look at possible distributions in section 3.

An intuitive way of characterizing these concepts is in form of graphs with the elements of the random vectors as vertices and the interactions as edges.

Figure 2: The fully connected system for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$.

For every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we are able to divide the set of vertices into subsets corresponding to their time steps. The connections between random variables of the same subset are undirected and the interactions between elements of the different subsets are directed. We have no directed circles and the elements of each subset induce undirected subgraphs, which are called chain components. Graphs of this form are called chain graphs in [33] section 2.1.1. In order to be able to see these qualities of the graphs three time steps $X := Z_t, Y := Z_{t+1}$ and $W := Z_{t+2}$ are displayed in Figure 3 with highlighted chain components.

Figure 3: The fully connected system for $n = 3$ and three timesteps with emphasized chain components.

We will take a closer look at graphs and the corresponding graphical models in section 2.3. Now we encounter two questions:

1. How do we determine the distance between two systems?
2. What does a disconnected system look like and what properties should it satisfy?

To answer the first question we need basic concepts from information theory and information geometry, which will be discussed in the next section. The second question is more difficult to answer and is therefore subject of recent research. In section 3 we will

take a look at different ways to define a system consisting of the sum of its parts and we will discuss some postulates regarding the properties of the resulting system, that have been made for example in [37].

2 Theoretical Foundations

Here we take a step back from the system introduced in the previous section and consider discrete probability distributions on finite sets in general. It is also possible to develop the following concepts for continuous probability distributions, see for example [7], but for the purpose of this thesis discrete probability distributions suffice.

2.1 Information Theory

The problem at hand is to compare two probability distributions. In order to be able to do this, we need a notion of distance between the amount of information contained in these distributions.

One of the main concepts of information theory is entropy. C. E. Shannon published in 1948 in “A Mathematical Theory of Communication” [43] an approach to a general theory of communication. There he studies a channel system displayed in Figure 4 consisting of an information source in which a message originates and gets passed on to a transmitter. This transmitter converts the message into a signal that might be disturbed by a noise source before it reaches the receiver and finally its destination.

Figure 4: Communication system.

One of Shannon’s goals was it to improve this transmission of information. Therefore he searched for the optimal rates of data transportation and compression without loss of information. His approach is to quantify how uncertain the outcome of a variable is. In this context he defined the entropy as lower bound for the compression. He postulates in chapter 6 of [43] three properties that such a measure $H(P)$ of uncertainty should hold, with P as the probability distribution that describes the occurrences of a set of possible events $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$:

1. H should be continuous in $P(x_i)$, $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$.

2. H should be a monotonic increasing function of n if all the $P(x_i)$ equal $\frac{1}{n}$.
3. H should be additive in the sense, that if a choice can be broken down into two successive choices, the original H should be the weighted sum of the individual values of H .

In [43] Theorem 2 he proves that this determines the entropy defined below up to a positive constant.

Definition 2 (Entropy). Let P be a probability distribution of a random variable X on \mathfrak{X} . The entropy is defined as follows

$$H_P(X) := - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} P(x) \log_2 P(x) \quad (2)$$

using the convention that $0 \cdot \log(0) = 0$.

The base of the logarithms does not matter in this context, because of the following result

Proposition 1. Let $H_{P,a}(X)$ be defined as the entropy with the logarithm with base a and let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}^+$. Then

$$H_{P,b}(X) = (\log_b a) H_{P,a}(X).$$

Proof. We have

$$H_{P,b}(X) = - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} P(x) \log_b P(x) = - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} P(x) (\log_b a) \log_a (P(x)) = (\log_b a) H_{P,a}(X).$$

□

As we have seen before, a constant factor does not change the the properties of the entropy. Note that the concept of entropy used in thermodynamics differs from the information theoretic definition only by a fixed constant, the Boltzmann constant.

Considering the goal of defining complexity measures, it will be necessary to define conditional entropy:

Definition 3 (Conditional Entropy). Let (X, Y) be a random vector with elementary events from $\mathfrak{X} \times \mathfrak{Y}$ and the probability distribution P . The conditional entropy is defined as

$$H_P(X | Y) := - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \log P(y|x). \quad (3)$$

The chain rule for entropy provides an intuitive notion of the connection between the entropy and the conditional entropy:

Proposition 2 (Chain Rule for Entropy). *Let (X, Y) be a random vector with elementary events from $\mathfrak{X} \times \mathfrak{Y}$ and the probability distribution P , then the following equality holds*

$$H_P(X, Y) = H_P(X) + H_P(Y|X).$$

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} H_P(X, Y) &= - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \log P(x, y) \\ &= - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \log (P(x) \cdot P(y|x)) \\ &= - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} P(x) \log P(x) - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \log P(y|x) \\ &= H_P(X) + H_P(Y|X). \end{aligned}$$

□

Another key concept is the KL-divergence (Kullback-Leibler-divergence) also known as relative entropy.

Definition 4 (KL-Divergence). Let P and Q be two probability distributions of random variables on \mathfrak{X} . The Kullback-Leibler-divergence is defined as

$$D_{\mathfrak{X}}(P \parallel Q) := \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} P(x) \log \left(\frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$= \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} P(x) \log \frac{1}{Q(x)} - H_P(X) \quad (5)$$

with the conventions, that $0 \cdot \log \frac{0}{0} = 0$, $0 \cdot \log \frac{0}{Q(x)} = 0$ and $P(x) \log \left(\frac{P(x)}{0} \right) = \infty$ for $P(x) \neq 0$.

The first summand in (5) is called cross entropy.

Definition 5 (Cross Entropy). Let P and Q be two probability distributions of random variables on \mathfrak{X} . The cross entropy is defined as

$$H_{P,Q}(X) := \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} P(x) \log \frac{1}{Q(x)}. \quad (6)$$

So by subtracting the actual entropy from the cross entropy, we gain a value for how much the uncertainty increases, if we use Q instead of P . Hence the KL-divergence $D_{\mathfrak{X}}(P \parallel Q)$ measures how inefficient it would be to use the probability distribution Q instead of the true distribution P . Similar to the entropy it is possible to gain the definition of KL-divergence by an axiomatic description. See [19] for a discussion of different axiomatic approaches.

Additionally, the KL-divergence holds the following properties.

Proposition 3. *Let P and Q be probability distributions on a set \mathfrak{X} . Then the following holds.*

- $D_{\mathfrak{X}}(P \parallel Q) \geq 0$
- $D_{\mathfrak{X}}(P \parallel Q) = 0 \iff P = Q$

Proof. See [16] Theorem 2.6.3. □

Definition 6 (Complexity). Let M be a set of probability distributions. Then we choose the probability distribution $P^* \in M$, that holds the minimal divergence to the distribution of the fully connected system P to calculate the complexity

$$\Phi(P) := \inf_{Q \in M} D_{\mathfrak{X}}(P \parallel Q) = D_{\mathfrak{X}}(P \parallel P^*). \quad (7)$$

In Section 3 the set M will consist of those distributions that belong to the disconnected system, meaning the system divided in parts. The more the fully connected system differs from the disconnected one, the more complex we call it.

The minimization with respect to the second argument is also called rI-projection, reverse Information projection [21]. Minimizing with respect to the first argument is called I-projection, Information projection. We will look at this in Section 2.2 in more detail.

We will also use a special case of KL-divergence, the mutual information.

Definition 7 (Mutual Information). Let (X, Y) be a random vector on $\mathfrak{Z} = \mathfrak{X} \times \mathfrak{Y}$, $P(X, Y)$ the probability distribution of them and the marginal distributions $P(X), P(Y)$. Then we gain the mutual information by calculating the KL-divergence between $P(X, Y)$

and the product distribution $P(X)P(Y)$:

$$I(X; Y) := D_{\mathfrak{Z}}(P(X, Y) \parallel P(X)P(Y)) \quad (8)$$

$$= \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \log \left(\frac{P(x, y)}{P(x)P(y)} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$= H_P(X) - H_P(X|Y) \quad (10)$$

Shannon introduces this concept in [43] in chapter 12 as the rate of actual transmission in the case of a signal that has been disturbed by some noise. There he considers $H_P(X)$ to be the entropy of the source signal and $H_P(Y)$ as the entropy of the output signal.

Additionally, it is possible to define a conditional version of the KL-divergence, similar to the conditional entropy.

Definition 8 (Conditional KL-Divergence). Let P and Q be two probability distributions of random variables with elementary events from $\mathfrak{X} \times \mathfrak{Y}$. The conditional KL-divergence is defined as

$$D_{\mathfrak{Y}|\mathfrak{X}}(P \parallel Q) := \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \log \left(\frac{P(y|x)}{Q(y|x)} \right). \quad (11)$$

Similar to the chain-rule of the entropy, we are able to define such a rule for the KL-divergence.

Proposition 4 (Chain-Rule for KL-Divergence). Let P and Q be two probability distributions of random variables with elementary events from $\mathfrak{Z} = \mathfrak{X} \times \mathfrak{Y}$. Then the following chain-rule holds:

$$D_{\mathfrak{Z}}(P \parallel Q) = D_{\mathfrak{X}}(P \parallel Q) + D_{\mathfrak{Y}|\mathfrak{X}}(P \parallel Q).$$

Proof. See Theorem 2.5.3 in [16]. □

There exist helpful connections between the KL-divergence and the entropy for the joint and the conditional case. To prove these, we need the Jensen's inequality:

Definition 9 (Jensen's Inequality). If f is a convex function, X a random variable with values in $\mathfrak{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ with probability distribution P and E the expectation $EX = \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} P(x)x$, then

$$Ef(X) \geq f(EX).$$

If f is strictly convex, then equality implies that $X = EX$, with probability 1 and therefore that X is a constant.

Proof. See [16] Theorem 2.6.2. □

Now we are able to prove the following proposition.

Proposition 5. *Let P and Q be two probability distributions of random variables with elementary events from $\mathfrak{X} \times \mathfrak{Y}$. Then the following properties hold:*

- (1) $D_{\mathfrak{X}}(P \parallel Q) = H_{P,Q}(X) - H_P(X) \geq 0$
- (2) $D_{\mathfrak{Y}|\mathfrak{X}}(P \parallel Q) = - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \log Q(y | x) - H_P(Y | X) \geq 0$

Proof. (1) Proposition 3 states that $D_{\mathfrak{X}}(P \parallel Q) \geq 0$. The equality holds because of

$$\begin{aligned} H_{P,Q}(X) - H_P(X) &= - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} P(x) \log Q(x) + \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} P(x) \log P(x) \\ &= \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} P(x) \log \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)}. \end{aligned}$$

(2) Similar to (1) we are able to write

$$\begin{aligned} - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \log Q(y | x) - H_P(Y | X) &= - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \log Q(y | x) \\ &\quad + \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \log P(y | x) \\ &= \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \log \left(\frac{P(y | x)}{Q(y | x)} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Using the Jensen's inequality from Definition 9 leads to

$$\begin{aligned} - \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \log \left(\frac{P(y | x)}{Q(y | x)} \right) &\leq \log \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} P(x, y) \frac{Q(y | x)}{P(y | x)} \\ &= \log \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} \cdot Q(x, y) \\ &= \log \sum_{x \in \mathfrak{X}} \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} \sum_{y \in \mathfrak{Y}} Q(x, y) \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence we have $D_{\mathfrak{g}|\mathfrak{x}}(P \parallel Q) \geq 0$. □

2.2 Information Geometry

In the previous section we introduced the KL-divergence as a notion of difference between two distributions, although it is not symmetric and does not satisfy a triangular inequality. The reason for the use of the KL-divergence can be found in information geometry, where tools from differential geometry get introduced to structures consisting of probability distributions.

In order to do this, we will first take a look at statistical models. A statistical model is a set of probability distributions on a sample set \mathcal{Z} parameterized by $\theta = (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_n)$:

$$\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}, \theta) := \{P_\theta \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})\}.$$

One well known example of a statistical model is the set of normal distributions:

Example (Normal Distributions). The family of normal distributions

$$\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}, (\mu, \sigma)) := \left\{ P_{(\mu, \sigma)}(z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-\frac{(z-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \mid \mu \in \mathbb{R}, 0 < \sigma \in \mathbb{R} \right\}$$

is parameterized by $\theta = (\mu, \sigma)$.

Now we are going to look at discrete distributions on a finite sample set \mathcal{Z} with cardinality $|\mathcal{Z}| = m + 1$ in general. Of course we are able to write every $P \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$ of those distributions as a vector of its values on the sample set \mathcal{Z} : $P(z) = (P(z_1), \dots, P(z_{m+1}))$. Because of the restriction, that

$$\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) = 1,$$

it suffices to use m values and therefore we gain a parametrization θ in a m -dimensional subspace of \mathbb{R}^n , $n \geq m$. For $m = 2$ and $m = 3$ we see the corresponding manifolds in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The m -dimensional manifolds corresponding to the discrete probability distributions with $m = 2$ and $m = 3$, from [2] Fig. 1.3.

Additionally, this parametrization is a one-to-one map from $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$ to \mathcal{R}^m and therefore there exists an inverse function from the image of ϕ , denoted by $im(\phi)$ to $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$

$$\phi : \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m, \quad P(z) \mapsto (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_m) = (P(z_1), \dots, P(z_m)) \quad (12)$$

$$\phi^{-1} : im(\phi) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}), \quad (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_m) \mapsto \left(P(z_1), \dots, P(z_{m-1}), 1 - \sum_{i=1}^m P(z_m) \right) = P(z).$$

If we look at this from the point of view of differential geometry, we can call this parametrization a coordinate system of the set $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$. In fact, the interior $\mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$ of $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$ is a differentiable manifold, following the Definition 2.1.1 from [11]:

Definition 10 (Differentiable Manifold). Let V be a subset of \mathbb{R}^n , $n, m \in \mathbb{N}$. V is an m -dimensional C^p submanifold of \mathbb{R}^n if there exists for every $x \in V$ an open neighborhood $U \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ of x and a map $f : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $f(U) \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$ is open, f is a C^p diffeomorphism onto its image and $f(U \cap V) = f(U) \cap \mathbb{R}^n$. The ordered pair (U, f) is called a chart.

It is easy to see, that the coordinate system θ fulfills the conditions in the definition for $\mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$. This set has not only the structure of an differential manifold, but also of a Riemannian manifold. We will introduce the necessary concepts in the way of the chapters 2.1 and 2.2 from [7]. First, we need to look at a basis $\{e_z \mid z \in \mathcal{Z}\}$ of the vector space $\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$:

$$e_z(x) := \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } z = x \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}.$$

This is a basis since we are able to write every $f \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$ as:

$$f(x) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} f(z) \cdot e_z(x), \quad x \in \mathcal{Z}.$$

Let $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$ be the dual space, meaning the space of the real-valued linear functions on $\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$. Then $\{\delta_z \mid z \in \mathcal{Z}\}$ forms with the Dirac-measures

$$\delta_z(e_x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } z = x \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

a basis for $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$, because we are able to write every $g \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$ as

$$g(\cdot) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} g(e_z) \delta_z(\cdot). \quad (13)$$

Applying this to a function $f \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$ leads to

$$g(f) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} g(e_z) \delta_z \left(\sum_{z' \in \mathcal{Z}} f(z') \cdot e_{z'} \right) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} g(e_z) f(z) \delta_z(e_z).$$

Hence every element of $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$ can be written as a linear combination of Dirac-measures and therefore can be seen as a measure, if it is non-negative. This leads to an isomorphism between $\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$ and $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$

$$e_z \mapsto \delta_z \quad (14)$$

and we will define $g(z) := g(e_z)$ for $g \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$. Therefore, we are able to rewrite $\mathcal{P}^0(\mathcal{Z})$ as

$$\mathcal{P}^0(\mathcal{Z}) = \left\{ P \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z}) : P(z) > 0 \text{ for all } z \in \mathcal{Z}, \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) = 1 \right\}.$$

Now we take a look at the tangent space, following the Definition 2.5.1. of [11]:

Definition 11 (Tangent Space). Let V be a submanifold of \mathbb{R}^n . A vector $z \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is tangential to V at $x \in V$ if there exists a C^1 curve $\alpha : I \rightarrow V$, $0 \in I$ such that $\alpha(0) = x$ and $\alpha'(0) = z$. The set of tangent vectors to V at x is a vector subspace of \mathbb{R}^n and is called tangent space to V at x : $T_x V$.

Differentiating an element of $\mathcal{P}^0(\mathcal{Z})$ with respect to a curve at a point P leads to the following tangent space

$$T_P(\mathcal{Z}) = \{P\} \times \left\{ Q \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z}) : \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} Q(z) = 0 \right\}$$

because of the normalization of the probability distributions.

A Riemannian-metric describes the intrinsic structure of the manifold and is therefore defined with respect to the tangent space at each point. Hence we now fix one $P \in \mathcal{P}^0(\mathcal{Z})$. Given this element, we are able to define a product on $\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$

$$\langle f, g \rangle_P := \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} f(z)g(z)P(z). \quad (15)$$

In (14) we have already seen an isomorphism between $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$ and $\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$. The product above leads to the definition of a map from $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$ to $\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$.

Proposition 6. *Let $g \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$ then*

$$g \mapsto \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{g(z)}{P(z)} e_z(\cdot)$$

defines another isomorphism between $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$ and $\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$.

Proof. The sum is well defined because of $P \in \mathcal{P}^0(\mathcal{Z})$ and the sum is only zero for every $z \in \mathcal{Z}$, if g maps every e_z to zero. Considering the representation (13), this is only the case if g is already the zero map. Therefore this map is injective and because of the existing isomorphism bijective. Now let us consider two $g, h \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$, then

$$g + h = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} (g(z) + h(z)) \delta_z \mapsto \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{g(z) + h(z)}{P(z)} e_z(\cdot) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{g(z)}{P(z)} e_z(\cdot) + \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{h(z)}{P(z)} e_z(\cdot)$$

and also the homogeneity holds. □

Now it is possible to use this isomorphism in order to define an inner product similar to (15) also for $g, h \in \mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$

$$\left\langle \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{g(z)}{P(z)} e_z(\cdot), \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{h(z)}{P(z)} e_z(\cdot) \right\rangle_P = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{g(z)h(z)}{P(z)} e_z(\cdot)$$

$$\langle g, h \rangle_P := \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{g(z)h(z)}{P(z)}.$$

This leads to the desired metric.

Definition 12 (Fisher Metric). The Fisher metric $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_P : T_P(\mathcal{Z}) \times T_P(\mathcal{Z}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ at $P \in \mathcal{P}^0(\mathcal{Z})$ is defined as:

$$(x, y) \mapsto \langle x, y \rangle_P = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{1}{P(z)} x(z)y(z), \quad x, y \in T_P(\mathcal{Z})$$

Following the Definition 1.5 of [55] a Riemannian Manifold is defined below.

Definition 13 (Riemannian Manifold). Let M be a differentiable manifold, $T_P M$ the tangent space at the point $P \in M$ and g a family of inner products g_P on $T_P M$, meaning functions

$$g_P : T_P M \times T_P M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

that are linear, symmetric and positive definite. Additionally, g_P depends smoothly on P in the sense that for C^∞ vector fields X, Y the mapping $p \mapsto \langle X_P, Y_P \rangle$ is a C^∞ function on M .

Lemma 1. *The manifold $\mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$ and the family of inner products defined by the Fisher metric form a Riemannian manifold.*

Proof. After Definition 10 we have already seen that $\mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$ is a differentiable manifold. The symmetry and positive definiteness is obvious. For the linearity take $P \in \mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$, $f, g, h \in T_P M$, $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \langle a \cdot f + b \cdot g, h \rangle_P &= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{1}{P(z)} (a \cdot f(z) + b \cdot g(z)) h(z) \\ &= a \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{1}{P(z)} f(z) h(z) + b \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{1}{P(z)} g(z) h(z) \\ &= a \cdot \langle f, h \rangle_P + b \cdot \langle g, h \rangle_P \end{aligned}$$

Additionally, the mapping depends smoothly on $P \in \mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$. □

Although fixing the basis for $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{Z})$ and $\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$ was necessary in order to construct the structures above, the resulting Fisher metric is independent of those. It is possible to extend the definition of the Fisher metric to the closed $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$, this has been done in Section 2.2 of [7].

The Fisher metric is often presented in another way. Consider for that the Fisher metric as an example of a covariant 2-tensor using Definition 2.2 from [7].

Definition 14 (Covariant 2-Tensor). A covariant 2-tensor Θ on a manifold M is a collection of 2-multilinear maps:

$$\Theta_P : T_P M \times T_P M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad (v_1, v_2) \mapsto \Theta_P(V_1, V_2)$$

with $P \in M$ and $V_1, V_2 \in T_P M$ such that this is continuous in the sense that for continuous vector fields V_1, V_2 the function $P \mapsto \Theta_P(V_1, V_2)$ is continuous.

Covariant 2-tensors can be pulled back from a manifold M_2 to a manifold M_1 , if there exists a differentiable map $f : M_1 \rightarrow M_2$. Let $\xi \in M_2$, then the pullback of the 2-tensor to M_1 is

$$f^*(\Theta)_\xi(V_1, V_2) := \Theta_{f(\xi)} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial V_1}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial V_2} \right)$$

Now taking a submanifold M of $\mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$ and the embedding $M \hookrightarrow \mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$, $\xi \mapsto P_\xi(\cdot) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P_\xi(z) \delta_z(\cdot)$ leads to the pullback of the Fisher metric \mathfrak{g} to a metric on M . For $V_1, V_2 \in T_\xi M$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} g_\xi(V_1, V_2) &:= P^*(\mathfrak{g})_\xi(V_1, V_2) \\ &= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \frac{1}{P_\xi(z)} \frac{\partial P_\xi(z)}{\partial V_1} \frac{\partial P_\xi(z)}{\partial V_2} \\ &= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P_\xi(z) \frac{\partial \log(P_\xi(z))}{\partial V_1} \frac{\partial \log(P_\xi(z))}{\partial V_2}. \end{aligned}$$

Using the coordinate system θ from (12) and $\partial_i := \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_i}$ we are able to define the Fisher information matrix as

$$\mathfrak{g}_{i,j}(P) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \partial_i \log P(z) \partial_j \log P(z), \quad i, j \in \{1, \dots, m\}.$$

The Fisher metric not only provides $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$ with a Riemannian structure, but has other useful properties. It was introduced by Rao in 1945, republished in [42], and is also known as Shahshahani metric in biology. If we consider a statistical model $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}, \theta)$, the problem of finding the parameters of a distribution belonging to data from a sample set arises in statistical estimation. In this setting, the Cramér-Rao inequality shows that the reciprocal of the Fisher information matrix bounds the mean-squared error of any unbiased estimator from below, see for example [7] in Section 5.2 or [16] in Section 11.10. Hence the Fisher metric quantifies how sensitive the dependency of the parameters on the samples in \mathcal{Z} is.

Additionally, the Fisher metric is uniquely determined, up to a constant factor, by the property of being invariant under sufficient statistics, see [7] Theorem 1.2. Sufficient statistics are maps from the sample space to a possibly smaller sample space that have the property that sampling from the new sample space does not change the quality of the process of identifying the parameter. Other properties that uniquely determine the Fisher information matrix are its invariance under reparametrizations of the sample space \mathcal{Z} and the fact that it is covariant under reparametrizations of the parameter space [15].

The Fisher metric is also closely connected to the KL-divergence in the following sense.

Lemma 2. *Let $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}, \theta)$ be a statistical model. If θ and $\theta + \Delta\theta$ are sufficiently close and if the parameter space is an open convex set, then the KL-divergence $D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P_{\theta} \parallel P_{\theta+\Delta\theta})$ can be expressed as quadratic form with coefficients defined by the Fisher information matrix.*

Proof. A proof can be found in [31] in Section 6. □

2.2.1 Exponential Families and Mixture Families

Now we are going to look at two dual families of probability distributions, that have a direct relation to the Fisher metric. At first we will consider another coordinate system for $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$. It is possible to write every discrete distribution with $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq S(P)$ in form of an exponential function

$$P(z) = \frac{1}{Z(h)} e^{h(z)},$$

$$Z(h) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} e^{h(z)}$$

where $h \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$ and $Z(h)$ is a normalizing factor. Trivially, we could define h for a discrete distribution P as:

$$h(z) := \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{Z}|} \lambda_i \delta_i(z) \quad \lambda_i := \ln(P(z_i)) \quad \delta_i(z) := \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } z = z_i \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

this leads to $Z(h) = 1$ and

$$P(z_i) = e^{\sum_{i=1}^{|\mathcal{Z}|} \lambda_i \delta_i(z_i)}.$$

Of course we are able to define

$$\lambda_{|\mathcal{Z}|} = \ln \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^m P(z_i) \right) = \ln \left(1 - \sum_{j=1}^m e^{\sum_{i=1}^m \lambda_i \delta_i(z_j)} \right)$$

and with that we get another m -dimensional coordinate system $\lambda = (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_m)$ defined by

$$\phi : \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m, \quad P(z) \mapsto (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_m) = (\ln(P(z_1)), \dots, \ln(P(z_m)))$$

$$\phi^{-1} : im(\phi) \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}), \quad (\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_m) \mapsto (e^{\lambda_1}, \dots, e^{\lambda_m}, e^{\lambda_{m+1}}) = P(z)$$

that also forms a differentiable manifold with $\mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$. We have seen that we could interpret the set of δ as a basis for a linear space. Now we are going to take a linear subspace to define exponential families.

Definition 15 (Exponential Family). Given a reference measure $P^0 \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$, $S(P) = \mathcal{Z}$ and a basis $f = \{f_1, \dots, f_k\}$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $k \leq n$ of a linear subspace of $\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$. The corresponding exponential family is denoted by

$$\mathcal{E}(f, P^0) := \left\{ P_{\lambda, P^0} \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \mid P_{\lambda, P^0}(z) = \frac{1}{Z_{P^0}(\lambda \cdot f)} e^{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i f_i(z)} P^0(z), \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^k, z \in \mathcal{Z} \right\}$$

with the normalizing factor

$$Z_{P^0}(\lambda \cdot f) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} e^{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i f_i(z)} P^0(z).$$

Given a fixed basis f the distributions belonging to $\mathcal{E}(f, P^0)$ are uniquely defined by the parameters λ_i , $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, because the f_i are pairwise linearly independent. These parameters are called the canonical or natural parameters of the exponential family. Taking those as coordinates, we are able to look at exponential families as submanifolds of $\mathcal{P}^0(\mathcal{Z})$. Rewriting the normalizing factor leads to

$$P_{\lambda}(z) = e^{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i f_i(z) + \ln(P^0(z)) - \psi(\lambda)},$$

$$\psi(\lambda) = \ln \left(\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} e^{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i f_i(z) + \ln(P^0(z))} \right). \quad (17)$$

This function ψ is also called ‘‘cumulant generating function’’ in statistics or ‘‘free energy’’ in statistical mechanics, see for example [32] in Section 3, and has the following properties.

Lemma 3. *Let $\mathcal{E}(f, P^0)$ be an exponential family with the free energy function ψ as defined in (17). Then this function satisfies the following properties:*

- The function ψ is convex.
- The Hessian matrix of ψ equals the Fisher information matrix.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_j} \psi(\lambda) = \mathfrak{g}_{i,j}(P_{\lambda})$$

Proof. By differentiating the identity

$$\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P_{\lambda}(z) = 1 \quad (18)$$

with respect to λ_i we gain the following relations

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \left(f_i(z) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_i} \psi(\lambda) \right) P_\lambda(z) &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_i} \psi(\lambda) &= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} f_i(z) P_\lambda(z) = E_{P_\lambda}[f_i], \\ \nabla \psi(\lambda) &= E_{P_\lambda}[f],\end{aligned}$$

with $E_P[f_i] := \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} f_i(z) P(z)$ the expectation value of f_i given P . Differentiating (18) again with respect to λ_j leads to

$$\begin{aligned}\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \left(f_j(z) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_j} \psi(\lambda) \right) \left(f_i(z) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_i} \psi(\lambda) \right) P_\lambda(z) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_j} \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_i} \psi(\lambda) P_\lambda(z) &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_j} \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_i} \psi(\lambda) &= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \left(f_j(z) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_j} \psi(\lambda) \right) \left(f_i(z) - \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_i} \psi(\lambda) \right) P_\lambda(z) \quad (19)\end{aligned}$$

$$= E[(f_j - E_{P_\lambda}[f_j])(f_i - E_{P_\lambda}[f_i])^T] \quad (20)$$

$$\nabla \nabla \psi(\lambda) = E[(f - E_{P_\lambda}[f])(f - E_{P_\lambda}[f])^T] \quad (21)$$

Additionally, the following holds

$$\begin{aligned}\partial_i \log P_\lambda(z) &= f_i(z) - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} f_i(z) P_\lambda(z) \\ &= f_i(z) - E_{P_\lambda}[f_i].\end{aligned}$$

Combining these and the definition of the Fisher information matrix, we gain:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathfrak{g}_{i,j}(P) &= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P_\lambda(z) \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_i} \log P_\lambda(z) \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_j} \log P_\lambda(z) \\ &= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P_\lambda(z) (f_i(z) - E_{P_\lambda}[f_i]) (f_j(z) - E_{P_\lambda}[f_j]) \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_i} \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_j} \psi(\lambda).\end{aligned}$$

Since the second derivatives are given by the Fisher metric and therefore positive definite, ψ is a convex function. We saw the positive definiteness of the Fisher metric in Lemma 1. \square

Additionally, we are able to fix the expected values on f :

$$\begin{aligned}\eta_i(\lambda) &:= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P_\lambda(z) f_i(z) \\ &= E_{P_\lambda}[f_i] \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_i} \psi(\lambda)\end{aligned}$$

these are called the expectation parameters or dual parameters. In the next section, we are going to look at the concept of dual coordinate systems like this in a more general sense.

The following definition describes another family of probability distributions that plays a dual role to the exponential families.

Definition 16 (Mixture Families). Let $f = \{f_1, \dots, f_k\}$, $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $k \leq n$ be a basis of a linear subspace of $\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$ then the corresponding mixture family is

$$M(\eta) := \left\{ P_\eta \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \mid P_\eta(z) = c(z) + \sum_{i=1}^k f_i(z) \eta_i, \quad \eta \in \mathbb{R}^k \right\}$$

with a regularization function $c \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$ that has to be adjusted in order to gain that $P_\eta \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$.

The full simplex of discrete distributions is a mixture family, because we are able to define for every $P \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$ the basis f as consisting of the $\delta_i(z)$ we used in (16) and $\eta_i := P(z_i)$. This leads to

$$P_\eta(z) = \sum_{i=1}^m \delta_i(z_i) P(z_i) + \delta_{m+1}(z_{m+1}) \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^m \delta_i(z_i) P(z_i) \right), \quad \forall z \in \mathcal{Z}.$$

To understand the dual structure of these two families, we need the following definitions from [55] Section 6, [12] Section 8.11 and [28] Section 4.1 .

Definition 17 (Affine Connections). Let $\mathfrak{T}(M)$ be the set of all C^∞ vector fields on a manifold M . Then a \mathbb{R} -bilinear map

$$\nabla : \mathfrak{T}(M) \times \mathfrak{T}(M) \rightarrow \mathfrak{T}(M)$$

written $\nabla_X Y$ for $\nabla(X, Y)$, $X, Y \in \mathfrak{T}(M)$ is called an affine connection, if it satisfies the following properties:

- (i) $\nabla_X Y$ is \mathcal{F} -linear in X
- (ii) $\nabla_X Y$ satisfies the Leibnitz rule in Y , for $f \in \mathcal{F}$

$$\nabla_X(fY) = (Xf)Y + f\nabla_X Y$$

with \mathcal{F} as the ring of C^∞ functions on M .

Definition 18 (Flat Connection). A connection ∇ is called flat if there are for each point local coordinates ξ_1, \dots, ξ_k and a neighbourhood U such that the coordinate vector fields are parallel on U , meaning that

$$\nabla \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi_i} = 0, \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, k\}.$$

Definition 19 (Dual Connections). Let (M, g) be a manifold with a Riemannian metric and two affine connections ∇, ∇^* . They are called dual with respect to the metric g , if

$$Zg(X, Y) = g(\nabla_Z X, Y) + g(X, \nabla_Z^* Y)$$

with X, Y, Z vector fields on M .

A dually flat submanifold is defined in the following way.

Definition 20 (Dually Flat Statistical Manifold). Let (M, g) be a Riemannian manifold and ∇, ∇^* two linear connections. A statistical manifold (M, g, ∇, ∇^*) is called dually flat if both dual connections are flat.

Now, we are able to look at the exponential and mixture families in this context. Let g be the Fisher metric and $\partial_i := \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda_i}$, the two connections $\nabla^{(1)}, \nabla^{(-1)}$ are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} g(\nabla_{\partial_i}^{(1)} \partial_j, \partial_k) &= E_{P_\lambda}[(\partial_i \partial_j \ln P_\lambda)(\partial_k \ln P_\lambda)] \\ g(\nabla_{\partial_i}^{(-1)} \partial_j, \partial_k) &= E_{P_\lambda}[(\partial_i \partial_j \ln P_\lambda + \partial_i \partial_j \ln P_\lambda)(\partial_k \ln P_\lambda)]. \end{aligned}$$

They belong to a more general family of α -connections, which are convex combinations of the connections above, see [7] Section 2.5.2 . These connections induce the following flat structures:

Proposition 7. *An exponential family as defined in Definition 15 is flat with respect to the connection $\nabla^{(1)}$.*

Proof. See [12] Proposition 1.9.1 . □

Proposition 8. *A mixture family as defined in Definition 16 is flat with respect to the connection $\nabla^{(-1)}$.*

Proof. See [12] Proposition 1.10.1 . □

These are dually flat because of the following result.

Proposition 9. *Given a statistical model, the Fisher metric g and vector fields X, Y, Z on it, the connections $\nabla^{(1)}$ and $\nabla^{(-1)}$ are dual*

$$Zg(X, Y) = g(\nabla_Z^{(1)} X, Y) + g(X, \nabla_Z^{(-1)} Y).$$

Proof. See [12] Proposition 1.10.4 . □

All in all, $\mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$ is a dually flat statistical manifold, the exponential families are flat submanifolds and the mixture families are dual flat submanifolds. Given the coordinates in (16), the dual coordinate system for $\mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$ is defined by the Legendre-Transformation with respect to the free-energy function:

$$\nabla\psi(\lambda_i) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P_\lambda(z) \delta_i(z) = P_\lambda(z_i) = \eta_i.$$

Additionally, the connections $\nabla^{(1)}, \nabla^{(-1)}$ are also known as ∇^e, ∇^m . It is possible to use these connections in a gradient based approach to divergences and derive the KL-divergence. In this approach the connections are used to define a difference vector X that translates one point to another and with that a vector field. By defining the vector field as the negative gradient field of a squared divergence function, one obtains the KL-divergence with respect to the first argument by using the ∇^e connection and by using the m -connection the KL-divergence with respect to the second argument

$$\begin{aligned} X^{(m)}(P, Q) &= -\text{grad}_P D_{\mathcal{Z}}(Q \parallel \cdot) \\ X^{(e)}(P, Q) &= -\text{grad}_P D_{\mathcal{Z}}(\cdot \parallel Q). \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, it is possible to show that the KL-divergence is the only function on the spaces of positive measures that satisfies these conditions, see [7] Proposition 2.11. For more details and proofs see [7] Sections 2.7.1 and 2.7.2. .

2.2.2 Geometric Results

Now we are able to define a few geometric results, which will be helpful in the next sections. Let M be a manifold, then we will examine a dual structure in general. To make it obvious that we are no longer considering exponential and mixture families, we will denote the points in M by ξ .

We will now look more closely on the definition of the KL-divergence. This divergence belongs to the more general family of Bregman-divergences.

The geometrical idea of these divergences is displayed in Figure 6. Let ϕ be a convex function. Then we can describe the tangent hyperplane in ξ_0 at the graph of ϕ as

$$z = \phi(\xi_0) + \nabla\phi(\xi_0) \cdot (\xi - \xi_0).$$

A Bregman-divergence describes the difference between the point ξ on the hyperplane to the graph of the the function ϕ .

Figure 6: Bregman-divergence (Fig. 1.4 from [2])

Definition 21 (Bregman-divergence). Let ϕ be a convex function and ξ, ξ_0 points on the hyperplane that is tangential to ϕ at the point ξ_0 . Then the Bregman-divergence is defined as

$$D_\phi[\xi : \xi_0] = \phi(\xi) - \phi(\xi_0) - \nabla\phi(\xi_0)(\xi - \xi_0).$$

Considering the convex function

$$\phi(\xi) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \xi(z) \log(\xi(z)) \tag{22}$$

we gain the KL-divergence defined in (3)

$$\begin{aligned}
D_\phi[\xi : \xi_0] &= \phi(\xi) - \phi(\xi_0) - \nabla\phi(\xi_0)(\xi - \xi_0) \\
&= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \xi(z) \log(\xi(z)) - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \xi_0(z) \log(\xi_0(z)) - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \log(\xi_0(z) + 1)(\xi(z) - \xi_0(z)) \\
&= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \xi(z) \log(\xi(z)) - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \xi_0(z) \log(\xi_0(z)) - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \xi(z) \log(\xi_0(z)) \\
&\quad + \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \xi_0(z) \log(\xi_0(z)) - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} (\xi(z) - \xi_0(z)) \\
&= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \xi(z) \log(\xi(z)) - \xi(z) \log(\xi_0(z)) \\
&= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \xi(z) \log \left(\frac{\xi(z)}{\xi_0(z)} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Using the free energy function ψ from (17) of an exponential family as ϕ leads to the dual of the KL-divergence

$$\begin{aligned}
D_\psi[\lambda : \lambda^0] &= \ln \left(\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} e^{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i f_i(z) + \ln(P^0(z))} \right) - \ln \left(\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} e^{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i^0 f_i(z) + \ln(P^0(z))} \right) \\
&\quad + \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P_{\lambda^0} f(z) (\lambda^0 - \lambda) \\
&= \ln \left(\frac{Z_{P^0}(\lambda f)}{Z_{P^0}(\lambda^0 f)} \right) \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P_{\lambda^0}(z) + \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P_{\lambda^0}(z) \ln e^{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i^0 f_i(z) - \lambda_i f_i(z) + \ln(P^0(z)) - \ln(P^0(z))} \\
&= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P_{\lambda^0}(z) \ln \frac{P_{\lambda^0}(z)}{P_\lambda(z)} \\
&= D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P_{\lambda^0} \parallel P_\lambda). \tag{23}
\end{aligned}$$

Now we are getting back to the function defined in (22). By fixing one ϕ we are able to uniquely identify one point in M with his normal vector regarding ϕ . Hence, we are able to define another coordinate system

$$\xi^* := \nabla\phi(\xi).$$

This operation is called the Legendre-Transformation and induces a dual coordinate system, as we have seen in the previous section. Using the Legendre-Transformation we are able to define the following convex function:

$$\phi^*(\xi^*) = \xi \cdot \xi^* - \phi(\xi) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \xi(z) \cdot \xi^*(z) - \phi(\xi). \tag{24}$$

This yields the dualistic structure (see [2] in Section 1.4):

$$\xi^* := \nabla\phi(\xi) \quad \xi = \nabla\phi^*(\xi^*)$$

and ϕ^* is also called Legendre-dual. We are able to write the Bregman-divergence using this Legendre-dual:

$$D_\phi[P : Q] = \phi(\xi_P) + \phi^*(\xi_Q^*) - \xi_P \xi_Q^* \quad (\text{see [2] Theorem 1.1}) \quad (25)$$

with ξ_P as the coordinates of P in the coordinate system ξ and ξ_Q^* respectively.

Theorem 2.1 (Generalized Pythagorean Theorem from [7] Corollary 4.1). *Let D_ϕ be a Bregman-divergence, M a dually flat manifold and let P, Q and R be points with the property, that the dual geodesic connecting P and Q is orthogonal to the geodesic connecting Q and R , then the following relation holds*

$$D_\phi[R : P] = D_\phi[R : Q] + D_\phi[Q : P]. \quad (26)$$

Figure 7: Generalized orthogonal triangle (Fig. 1.7 from [2])

Proof. The term “geodesic” describes a straight line in this context and not the shortest path between two points. Therefore, we are able to describe the geodesic connecting Q and R in the following way

$$\xi_{QR} = (1 - t)\xi_Q + t\xi_R. \quad (27)$$

Two geodesics are orthogonal, if the respective tangent vectors are orthogonal. The tangent vector belonging to (27) is:

$$\frac{d\xi_{QR}}{dt} = \xi_R - \xi_Q.$$

Correspondingly, we gain for the dual geodesic between P and Q and their tangent vector:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{PQ}^* &= (1 - t)\xi_P^* + t\xi_Q^* \\ \frac{d\xi_{PQ}^*}{dt} &= \xi_Q^* - \xi_P^*. \end{aligned}$$

In conclusion, we have

$$(\xi_Q^* - \xi_P^*) \cdot (\xi_R - \xi_Q) = 0.$$

By substituting (25) and (24) into the formula of the Bregman-divergence we gain:

$$\begin{aligned} D_\phi[R : Q] + D_\phi[Q : P] - D_\phi[R : P] &= \phi(\xi_R) + \phi^*(\xi_Q^*) - \xi_R \xi_Q^* + \phi(\xi_Q) + \phi^*(\xi_P^*) - \xi_Q \xi_P^* - \phi(\xi_R) - \phi^*(\xi_P^*) + \xi_R \xi_P^* \\ &= \xi_Q \xi_Q^* - \xi_R \xi_Q^* - \xi_Q \xi_P^* + \xi_R \xi_P^* \\ &= (\xi_Q^* - \xi_P^*) \cdot (\xi_Q - \xi_R) \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

□

We will use this result in Section 3.1 combined with the following Projection Theorem:

Theorem 2.2 (Projection Theorem). *Let $P \in M$ and $S \subset M$ be a flat submanifold of the dually flat manifold M . The dual projection of P to S minimizes the divergence $D_\phi[P : R]$, $R \in S$ and is unique. Correspondingly, if S is a dual flat submanifold of a dually flat manifold M , then the projection of P to S is unique and minimizes the dual divergence $D_{\phi^*}[P : R]$, $R \in S$.*

The projection of P to S results in the point $P^* \in S$ such that the geodesic connection between P and P^* are orthogonal to S . The dual geodesic projection is defined in the same way in respect to the dual geodesic.

Proof. See [2] Theorem 1.4. □

In the case of an exponential family, we have the following Bregman-divergences:

$$\begin{aligned} D_\psi[\lambda : \lambda^0] &= D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P_{\lambda^0} \parallel P_\lambda) \\ D_{\psi^*}[\lambda : \lambda^0] &= D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P_\lambda \parallel P_{\lambda^0}) \end{aligned}$$

because of (23) and [2] Section 1.4 .

2.3 Graphical Models

Another useful quality of exponential families is, that we are able to define families that are represented by a graph. This chapter is based on Section 2 and 3 of [33] and Section 2.9 of [7]. Therefore we will first define a graph.

Definition 22 (Graph). A graph is a pair $G = (V, E)$, where V is a finite set of vertices and $E \subseteq V \times V$ the set of edges which are ordered pairs of distinct vertices. We are only looking at graphs without multiple edges and without loops.

If both $(\alpha, \beta) \in E$ and $(\beta, \alpha) \in E$ this is called an undirected edge and if only $(\alpha, \beta) \in E$ it is called directed and is denoted by an arrow $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$. A graph consisting only of directed edges is called directed graph and an undirected graph is a graph consisting only of undirected edges. An undirected graph is complete if every pair of distinct vertices is connected by an edge. A complete subset that is maximal with respect to \subseteq is called a clique and the set of cliques of a graph is denoted by $C(G)$.

Another kind of graph is the chain graph. This is a graph consisting of directed and undirected edges such that we are able to partition the vertex set into subsets $V = V_1 \cup \dots \cup V_m$ with the properties that all edges between different subsets are directed, all edges between vertices of the same chain component are undirected and that there are no directed cycles. As we already mentioned in Section 1.3 that the systems we are going to look at are chain graphs.

If two vertices are connected by and directed or undirected edge, they are called neighbours or adjacent. The set of neighbours of a vertex α is $ne(\alpha)$. A path from α to β of length n is a sequence $\alpha = \alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_n = \beta$ of distinct vertices such that $(\alpha_{i-1}, \alpha_i) \in E$. If there exists a path from α to β and not from β to α , then α is called an ancestor of β and lies in the set $an(\beta)$, while β is a descendent of α and lies in the set $de(\alpha)$. The non-descendants are denoted by $nd(\alpha) = V \setminus (de(\alpha) \cup \{\alpha\})$.

If an arrow points from α to β , then α is called the parent of β and β the child of α . The set of parents of a node β is denoted by $pa(\beta)$ and the set of children of a node α by $ch(\alpha)$. The boundary $bd(A)$ of a set $A \subseteq V$ is the set of vertices in $V \setminus A$ that are parents or neighbours to vertices in A . The closure of A is $cl(A) = A \cup bd(A)$. If $bd(\alpha) \subseteq A$ for all $\alpha \in A$ we call A an ancestral set. For any $A \subseteq V$ there exists a smallest ancestral set containing A , because the intersection of ancestral sets is again an ancestral set. This smallest ancestral set of A is denoted by $An(A)$.

Let G be a chain graph. The moral graph of G is an undirected graph denoted by G^m that consists of the same vertex set as G and in which two vertices α, β are connected if and only if either they were already connected by an edge in G or if there are vertices γ, δ belonging to the same chain component such that $\alpha \rightarrow \gamma$ and $\beta \rightarrow \delta$.

Let $A, B, S \subseteq C$, then S separates A from B if every path from an $\alpha \in A$ to a $\beta \in B$ intersect C . In this case we call S an (A, B) -separator.

Now we consider the vertices of a graph to be random variables. Let Z be the vector of n' random variables and \mathcal{Z} be a set of configurations

$$z := (z_1, \dots, z_{n'}) \in \mathcal{Z}, n' \in \mathbb{N}$$

of the vertices of G with the sample set \mathcal{Z} . For a subset

$$A = \{A_1, \dots, A_{k'}\} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n'\}$$

we denote by Z_A the vector of random variables $Z_A = (Z_{A_1}, \dots, Z_{A_{k'}})$ with the configurations $z := (z_{A_1}, \dots, z_{A_{k'}})$. The distributions represented by a graph are called a graphical model and are defined in the following way.

Definition 23 (Graphical Model). Let G be a graph and $\mathcal{F}(G)$ the vector space of functions $f \in \mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$ such that there exist functions ϕ_A on the configurations of the cliques $A \in C(G)$ with

$$f(z) = \sum_{A \in C(G)} \phi_A(z_A).$$

A graphical model $\mathcal{E}(G)$ is the exponential family generated by the vector space $\mathcal{F}(G)$

$$\mathcal{E}(G) := \left\{ P(z) = \frac{e^{f(z)}}{\sum_{z' \in \mathcal{Z}} e^{f(z')}} \mid f \in \mathcal{F}(G), z \in \mathcal{Z} \right\}.$$

A graph G encodes conditional independence properties, which are satisfied by the distributions of the graphical model $\mathcal{E}(G)$, these are called Markov properties. Given three disjoint sets $A, B, C \subseteq \{1, \dots, n'\}$ we say that Z_A and Z_B are stochastically independent given Z_C and write

$$Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_B \mid Z_C$$

with respect to the distribution $P \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$, if

$$P(z_A, z_B \mid z_C) = P(z_A \mid z_C)P(z_B \mid z_C), \quad \text{whenever } P(z_C) > 0. \quad (28)$$

Dawid introduced this notation in [24], in which he connects different fields in statistical theory using the concept of conditional independence. There are different types of these conditional independence properties.

Definition 24 (Conditional Independence Properties). Let P be a distribution on \mathcal{Z} and G an undirected graph. P satisfies the

- (P) pairwise Markov property, with respect to G , if for any pair (Z_i, Z_j) of non-adjacent vertices

$$Z_i \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_j \mid \mathcal{Z} \setminus \{Z_i, Z_j\}$$

holds.

- (L) local Markov property, with respect to G , if we have for every vertex $Z_i \in \mathcal{Z}$

$$Z_i \perp\!\!\!\perp \mathcal{Z} \setminus cl(Z_i) \mid bd(Z_i).$$

- (G) global Markov property, with respect to G , if for any triple $Z_A, Z_B, Z_S \subseteq \mathcal{Z}$ of disjoint subsets, Z_S separates Z_A from Z_B in G

$$Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_B \mid Z_S.$$

The relations between the properties are the following one

$$(G) \Rightarrow (L) \Rightarrow (P)$$

see Proposition 3.4 in [33]. In order to gain equivalency one needs additional assumptions. In the Hammersley Clifford Theorem this is the positivity of the distributions, [33] Theorem 3.9, and one result due to Pearl and Paz is the following: The Markov properties are all equivalent if for all disjoint subsets $A, B, C, D \subseteq \{1, \dots, n'\}$ the following holds:

$$Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_B \mid (Z_C \cup Z_D) \text{ and } Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_C \mid (Z_B \cup Z_D) \text{ then } Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp (Z_B \cup Z_C) \mid Z_D. \quad (29)$$

The graphs of the systems introduced in Section 1.3 consist of directed and undirected edges and are chain graphs. Therefore we have different Markov properties. For a more detailed discussion of the Markov properties of chain graphs, see [27].

Definition 25 (Chain Graph Markov Properties). Let P be a distribution on \mathcal{Z} and G a chain graph. P satisfies the

- (PC) pairwise chain Markov property, with respect to G , if for any pair of non-adjacent vertices (Z_i, Z_j) with $Z_j \in nd(Z_i)$

$$Z_i \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_j \mid nd(Z_i) \setminus Z_j$$

holds.

(LC) local chain Markov property, with respect to G , if for any vertex $Z_i \in Z$ the following holds

$$Z_i \perp\!\!\!\perp nd(Z_i) \mid bd(Z_i).$$

(GC) global chain Markov property, with respect to G , if for any triple (Z_A, Z_B, Z_S) of disjoint subsets of Z such that Z_S separates Z_A from Z_B in $(G_{An(Z_A \cup Z_B \cup Z_S)})^m$, the moral graph of the smallest ancestral set containing $Z_A \cup Z_B \cup Z_S$,

$$Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_B \mid Z_S$$

holds.

In the case of the chain graphs introduced in Section 1.3 with $Z = (X_1, \dots, X_n, Y_1, \dots, Y_n)$ we have $n' = 2n$. Let $I := \{1, \dots, n\}$. Now we are able to denote the complement of a random variable X_i in the vector (X_1, \dots, X_n) by $X_{I \setminus \{i\}} = (X_1, \dots, X_{i-1}, X_{i+1}, \dots, X_n)$.

2.4 Conditional Independence Statements

As seen above, we are able to write Markov properties in form of conditional independence statements. Dawid shows in [24] that conditional independence statements have some general properties. These following four are also called the conditional independence axioms.

Proposition 10. *The ternary relation $Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_B \mid Z_C$ has the following properties:*

(C1) *if $Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_B \mid Z_C$ then $Z_B \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_A \mid Z_C$ (symmetry).*

(C2) *if $Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_{B \cup D} \mid Z_C$ then $Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_B \mid Z_C$ (decomposition).*

(C3) *if $Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_{B \cup D} \mid Z_C$ then $Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_B \mid Z_{C \cup D}$ (weak union).*

(C4) *if $Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_B \mid Z_{C \cup D}$ and $Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_D \mid Z_C$ then $Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_{B \cup D} \mid Z_C$ (contraction).*

Proof. See Proposition 3.1.2 [25]. □

The phrase "axiom" is due to Pearl, who calls a set of triplets satisfying the properties above semi-graphoids. If additionally (29) holds, then these structures are called graphoids [41]. In [40] p. 88 Pearl conjectured that these four properties are closed

in the sense that there exists for every ternary relation holding the properties above a probability model P such that

$$P(z_A|z_B, z_C) = P(z_A|z_C), \quad \text{if and only if } Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_B \mid Z_C.$$

This was disproven by Studený in [45] by finding another independent property of probabilistic conditional independence that is not derivable from the four axioms. Additionally Studený showed in [44] that such an axiomatization is not possible in general.

One can also look at conditional independence statements from the perspective of algebraic statistics. The following brief introduction is based on [25] Section 3, [46] Section 4 and [29]. But first we will need the following short definitions, for a more detailed treatment see [17].

Definition 26 (Polynomial Ideal, Variety and Primary Decomposition). Let K be a field and $K[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ a polynomial ring. If $f_1, \dots, f_s \in K[x_1, \dots, x_n]$, then we call

$$\langle f_1, \dots, f_s \rangle = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^s h_i f_i \mid h_1, \dots, h_s \in K[x_1, \dots, x_n] \right\}$$

the polynomial ideal generated by f_1, \dots, f_s . That this is in fact an ideal can be found in [17] Section 4 Lemma 3. An ideal is called prime if whenever $f, g \in K[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ and $fg \in I$, then either $f \in I$ or $g \in I$. If $fg \in I$ implies that either $f \in I$ or $g^m \in I$ for some power $m > 0$, then I is called primary.

Let I be an ideal, then we are able to define the affine variety of this ideal by

$$V(I) = \{(a_1, \dots, a_n) \in K^n \mid f(a_1, \dots, a_n) = 0, \text{ for all } f \in I\}.$$

An affine variety is irreducible whenever we are able to write $V = V_1 \cup V_2$ with V_1, V_2 affine varieties, then $V = V_1$ or $V = V_2$.

A primary decomposition of an ideal I is an expression of I consisting of primary ideals:

$$I = \bigcap_{i=1}^r Q_i, \text{ with } Q_i \text{ primary.}$$

The primary decomposition of an ideal always exists and for the associated algebraic varieties it holds that $V(I) = \bigcap_{i=1}^r V(Q_i)$, see [17] Theorem 7 Section 6 and [29] Theorem 3.2.18.

Similar to the beginning of Section 2.2 we define the probability distributions as vector

$$P = (P(z_1), \dots, P(z_{|Z|})).$$

Now we look at Proposition 4.1.6 from [46]:

Proposition 11. *Let $A, B, C \subseteq I$ pairwise disjoint, then the conditional independence statement $Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_B \mid Z_C$ holds if and only if*

$$P(z_A, z_B, z_C) \cdot P(z'_A, z'_B, z_C) = P(z_A, z'_B, z_C) \cdot P(z'_A, z_B, z_C) \quad (30)$$

for all $z_A, z'_A \in \mathcal{Z}_A$, $z_B, z'_B \in \mathcal{Z}_B$ and $z_C \in \mathcal{Z}_C$.

Proof. See Proposition 4.1.6 from [46]. □

That 30 induces (28) is easy to see, because we are able to write

$$\begin{aligned} P(z_A, z_B \mid z_C) &= P(z_A \mid z_C)P(z_B \mid z_C) \\ P(z_A, z_B, z_C)P(z_C) &= P(z_A, z_C)P(z_B, z_C). \end{aligned}$$

Using this notation enables us to see a conditional independence statement as a system of quadratic polynomial equations in the probability distribution. Therefore, we are able to look at the ideal generated by these polynomials and its variety.

Definition 27 (Conditional Independence Ideal). The Ideal generated by all the quadratic polynomials (30) is called the conditional independence ideal

$$I_{\mathcal{Z}_A \perp\!\!\!\perp \mathcal{Z}_B \mid \mathcal{Z}_C}.$$

The set of all probability distributions satisfying the polynomial constraints is called conditional independence model and is the variety of the ideal $V(I_{\mathcal{Z}_A \perp\!\!\!\perp \mathcal{Z}_B \mid \mathcal{Z}_C})$.

For only one conditional independence statement the following holds:

Proposition 12. *The conditional independence model $I_{\mathcal{Z}_A \perp\!\!\!\perp \mathcal{Z}_B \mid \mathcal{Z}_C}$ for any conditional independence statement $Z_A \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_B \mid Z_C$ is a prime ideal and therefore $V(I_{\mathcal{Z}_A \perp\!\!\!\perp \mathcal{Z}_B \mid \mathcal{Z}_C})$ is an irreducible variety.*

Proof. See Proposition 3.3.6. in [29]. □

A more general conditional independence model is the family of probability distributions that satisfies the conditional independence statements $CI := \{A_1 \perp\!\!\!\perp B_1 \mid C_1, \dots\}$. One way of analyzing the structure of the corresponding conditional independence model is to look at the primary decomposition of the conditional independence ideal. An easy example given in [29] Section 3.3.1 is the following:

$$I_C := I_{X_1 \perp\!\!\!\perp X_3 \mid X_2} + I_{X_1 \mid X_3}.$$

It is possible to calculate the primary decomposition over \mathbb{Q} for binary variables using the program Macaulay2 and the code:

```

loadPackage "GraphicalModels"
S = markovRing(2,2,2)
L = {{{1},{3},{2}}, {{1},{3},{}}}
I = conditionalIndependenceIdeal(S,L)
primaryDecomposition I

```

This leads to the following decomposition

$$I_C = I_{X_1 \perp\!\!\!\perp X_3 | X_2} + I_{X_1 | X_3} = I_{\{X_1, X_2\} \perp\!\!\!\perp X_3} \cap I_{X_1 \perp\!\!\!\perp \{X_3, X_2\}}.$$

For the varieties this corresponds to

$$V(I_C) = V(I_{\{X_1, X_2\} \perp\!\!\!\perp X_3}) \cup V(I_{X_1 \perp\!\!\!\perp \{X_3, X_2\}}).$$

We will see another example in Section 3.6.

3 Complexity Measures

In this Section we will return to the systems introduced in Section 1.3 and, as a reminder, we use the following notation for the random vectors.

$$\begin{aligned}
X &= (X_1, \dots, X_n) := (X_{1,t}, \dots, X_{n,t}) \\
Y &= (Y_1, \dots, Y_n) := (X_{1,t+1}, \dots, X_{n,t+1}) \\
Z &:= (X, Y).
\end{aligned}$$

The probability distributions discussed here are discrete distributions of a discrete, stationary, n -dimensional Markov-process $(Z_t)_{t \in \mathbb{N}}$ on a finite set $\mathcal{Z} \neq \emptyset$, which is the Cartesian product of the sample spaces of $X_1, \dots, X_n, Y_1, \dots, Y_n$:

$$\mathcal{Z} = \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y} = \prod_{i=1}^n \mathcal{X}_i \times \prod_{i=1}^n \mathcal{Y}_i.$$

Denote the complement of X_i in X by $X_{I \setminus \{i\}} := (X_1, \dots, X_{i-1}, X_{i+1}, \dots, X_n)$. Corresponding to this notation $x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \in \mathcal{X}_{I \setminus \{i\}}$ describes the elementary events of $X_{I \setminus \{i\}}$. We will use the analogue notation in the case of Y and we will write $z \in \mathcal{Z}$ instead of

$$z = (x, y) := (x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i, y_{I \setminus \{i\}}) \in \mathcal{X}_i \times \mathcal{X}_{I \setminus \{i\}} \times \mathcal{Y}_i \times \mathcal{Y}_{I \setminus \{i\}} = \mathcal{Z}, i \in \{1, \dots, n\}.$$

Additionally, for we will denote by $Z_J := (Z_j)_{j \in J}$ for a subset $I \subseteq J$.

Now we will take a closer look at the fully connected model from Figure 8. We are able to distinguish between the connections in the following way:

Figure 8: The fully connected system for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$.

The dotted connections can be analyzed by studying the marginal distributions $P(X)$ and $P(Y)$.

The dashed and continuous arrows are the ones connecting two time steps. In [37] in Postulate 2 the authors state the following rule.

Postulate 1. *A valid disconnected system should satisfy the Markov condition*

$$Q(X_i, Y_j | X_{I \setminus \{i\}}) = Q(X_i | X_{I \setminus \{i\}})Q(Y_j | X_{I \setminus \{i\}}), \quad i \neq j \quad (31)$$

with $Q \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$.

This is the first step towards a disconnected model, because it makes sure that the dashed connection are removed. Those connections are also called the causal connections.

In [37] the authors postulate three parts of the course of action to define a disconnected model. The other two postulates were already taken into account in the last sections during the definition of complexity. They determine the approach via comparison of a connected and a disconnected model and the KL-divergence as a tool to do so.

3.1 Mutual Information

We now take a look at the concept of mutual information defined in Definition 9 in order to understand another property that has been postulated for complexity measures. The mutual information in this setting is defined as

$$I(X;Y) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(x,y) \log \left(\frac{P(x,y)}{P(x)P(y)} \right).$$

Let us now assume that we use mutual information to define a complexity measure. The mutual information is zero if and only if the random variables X and Y are independent. This property follows directly from the fact, that mutual information is a special case of the KL-divergence. Therefore, by minimizing the mutual information, we enforce the random vectors in the different time steps $t, t + 1$ to become independent from each other. In the form of graphs, this is displayed in Figure 9.

Figure 9: The disconnected models for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ in the context of mutual information.

Now we are able to define the set of disconnecting systems regarding the mutual information and with this the complexity measure:

$$M_I := \{Q \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \mid Q(X,Y) = Q(X)Q(Y)\}.$$

Proposition 13. *The complexity measure in the case of the mutual information results in the mutual information*

$$\Phi_{M_I} := \inf_{Q \in M_I} D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q) = I(X;Y).$$

Minimizing the KL-divergence corresponds to a rI-projection to a submanifold M_I as shown in Figure 10.

Proof. Let $P^*, Q \in M_I$ such that $P^* \neq Q$. Using the projection theorem 2.2 the following generalized Pythagorean theorem from theorem 2.1 holds

$$D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q) = D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^*) + D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P^* \parallel Q). \quad (32)$$

Figure 10: Figure 2 from [37]: information-projection of $p(X, Y)$ to M_I

Now we get

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &= D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q) - D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^*) - D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P^* \parallel Q) \\
&= \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} P(x, y) \log \left(\frac{P(x, y)}{Q(x, y)} \right) - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} P(x, y) \log \left(\frac{P(x, y)}{P^*(x, y)} \right) \\
&\quad - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} P^*(x, y) \log \left(\frac{P^*(x, y)}{Q(x, y)} \right) \\
&= \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} P(x, y) \log \left(\frac{P^*(x, y)}{Q(x, y)} \right) - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} P^*(x, y) \log \left(\frac{P^*(x, y)}{Q(x, y)} \right) \\
&= \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} (P(x, y) - P^*(x, y)) \log \left(\frac{P^*(x, y)}{Q(x, y)} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Because of $P^*, Q \in M_I$ we are able to divide the sums over \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y}

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &= \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} (P(x, y) - P^*(x, y)) \log \left(\frac{P^*(x, y)}{Q(x, y)} \right) \\
&= \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} (P(x, y) - P^*(x, y)) \left(\log \left(\frac{P^*(x)}{Q(x)} \right) + \log \left(\frac{P^*(y)}{Q(y)} \right) \right) \\
&= \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} (P(x) - P^*(x)) \log \left(\frac{P^*(x)}{Q(x)} \right) + \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} (P(y) - P^*(y)) \log \left(\frac{P^*(y)}{Q(y)} \right). \quad (33)
\end{aligned}$$

Using Theorem 1.5 from [2] we know that there exists a unique information projection P . The equality (33) holds for $P(X) = P^*(X)$, $P^*(Y) = P(Y)$. Hence the complexity

measure is the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
\inf_{Q \in M_I} D_Z(P \parallel Q) &= \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} P(x, y) \log \left(\frac{P(x, y)}{P(x)P(y)} \right) \\
&= \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} P(x, y) (\log(P(x, y)) - \log(P(x)) - \log(P(y))) \\
&= \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} P(x, y) \log(P(x, y)) - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} P(x, y) \log(P(x)) \\
&\quad - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} P(x, y) \log(P(y)) \\
&= -H_P(X, Y) + H_P(X) + H_P(Y).
\end{aligned}$$

Applying the chain rule for entropy from Proposition 2 leads to:

$$\begin{aligned}
\inf_{Q \in M_I} D_Z(P \parallel Q) &= -H_P(X, Y) + H_P(X) + H_P(Y) \\
&= H_P(X) - H_P(X | Y) \\
&= I(X; Y).
\end{aligned}$$

□

In conclusion, we are able to calculate this complexity measure and it satisfies the property that the dashed connections displayed in Figure 8 are removed. But additionally the continuous arrows are also removed, so that we are considering a disconnected model in which the different time steps are completely independent of each other. This leads to a measure that determines the total information interaction between two time steps. Hence it does not fit the goal to determine the influence of the causal connections, but it is natural to assume a complexity measure to be bounded by mutual information. Otherwise the calculated difference in information would exceed the total existing amount of information interaction between the steps. This leads to the second postulate.

Postulate 2.

$$\Phi(P) = \inf_{Q \in M_\Phi} D_Z(P \parallel Q) \leq I(X; Y).$$

This can be found for example in [37] formula 12 or [30] Section 3.

3.2 Sum of Transfer Entropies

Considering Postulate 1 it seems natural to disconnect the causal influences one at a time and then summing the resulting divergences up. This approach was discussed in [37]. We are able to define a distribution $P \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$, that describes a model where X_i and Y_j , $i \neq j$ are disconnected in the following way

$$P(Y_j|X) = P(Y_j|X_{I \setminus \{i\}})$$

and the corresponding model

$$M_{T_{ij}} = \{P \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \mid P(Y_j|X) = P(Y_j|X_{I \setminus \{i\}})\}.$$

Minimizing the KL-divergence with respect to this model leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{M_{T_{ij}}} &:= \inf_{Q \in M_{T_{ij}}} D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q) = H_P(Y_j|X_{I \setminus \{i\}}) - H(Y_j|X) \\ &= TE(X_i \rightarrow Y_j|X_{I \setminus \{i\}}) \end{aligned}$$

which is the conditional transfer entropy. A proof of this can be found in the supporting information of [37]. This seems to be an easy approach, but unfortunately it does not satisfy Postulate 2. An easy example from [37] shows, that the sum of the transfer entropies can exceed the mutual information. Consider binary variables $n = 2$, X_1, X_2 uniformly distributed, Y_1 is calculated by the AND-relation from X_1 and X_2 and Y_2 is calculated by a noisy AND-relation. This means that Y_1 is only 1 if $X_1 = 1$ and $X_2 = 1$ and 0 otherwise and that Y_2 shows the same behaviour with a certain probability. The results of increasing the noise level can be seen in Figure 11. We will discuss this example further in the end of Section 3.6.1

Figure 11: Comparison of different complexity measures with four binary nodes (Fig. 3 from [37])

This leads to the conclusion that the sum of transfer entropies is not a suitable complexity measure.

3.3 Stochastic Interaction

In this section we will discuss the complexity measure called “stochastic interaction” [6], “total information flow” [30] or “fully split model” [5] which was introduced by Ay in [6]. A similar measure was also introduced independently by Barrett and Seth [9].

The core idea is to allow only the connections among the random variables of the first time step and additionally the connections between X_i and Y_i , meaning the same random variable in different time steps. The last ones correspond to the continuous arrows in Figure 8.

The set of distributions satisfying these conditions can be defined as follows:

$$M_S := \left\{ Q \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \mid Q(Y \mid X) = \bigotimes_{i=1}^n Q(Y_i \mid X_i) \right\}.$$

Graphs of these models for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ are displayed in Figure 12.

Figure 12: The disconnected models for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ in the context of stochastic interaction.

The complexity measure can be calculated as follows

$$\Phi_{M_S} := \inf_{Q \in M_S} D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q) = \sum_{i=1}^n H_P(Y_i \mid X_i) - H_P(Y \mid X).$$

Proof. In [6] this result was proven for Markovian transition kernels which are functions K that satisfy for $A, B \subseteq I, B \neq \emptyset$

$$\begin{aligned} K &: \mathcal{Z}_A \times \mathcal{Z}_B \rightarrow [0, 1], \\ (z_A, z_B) &\mapsto K(z_B \mid z_A), \\ \sum_{z_B \in \mathcal{Z}_B} K(z_B \mid z_A) &= 1, \forall z_A \in \mathcal{Z}_A. \end{aligned}$$

Hence a conditional distribution can be seen as a Markovian transition kernel. Proposition 1 (i) and (ii) of [6] proof the above claim for Markovian transition kernels and

additionally that the probability distribution on \mathcal{X} remains the initial one. Using the chain rule for the KL-divergence from Proposition 4 results in

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_{M_S} &:= \inf_{Q \in M_S} D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q) \\
&= \inf_{Q \in M_S} D_{\mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) + \inf_{Q \in M_S} D_{\mathcal{Y}|\mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) \\
&= \inf_{Q \in M_S} D_{\mathcal{Y}|\mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^n H_P(Y_i | X_i) - H_P(Y | X).
\end{aligned}$$

□

In Figure 12 we see, that the connections among random variables of the same time step are removed, but if we have a dependency between X_i and X_j with $i \neq j$, then there exists also some dependency between Y_i and Y_j . Additionally, this does not consider the cases in which there is a common exterior influence on the Y 's as displayed in Figure 13.

Figure 13: The disconnected models for $n = 3$ with exterior influences

Both of these properties can result in a value for Φ_{M_S} that exceeds the mutual information and therefore violates Postulate 2. An Example for this behaviour can be found for example in [30], displayed here in Figure 14. The value of stochastic information, here denoted by IF for “Information Flow” exceeds the value of the mutual information I.

Figure 14: Comparison of different complexity measures with data generated by a Boltzmann machine with 5 nodes (Fig. 5.c from [30])

Considering these shortcomings this measure does not fully satisfy the properties a measure for integrated information should have, although it is a comprehensible approach that yields a measure which is easy to calculate. In Figure 14 we also see another complexity measure denoted by Φ_G . This is the one that tries to resolve the issues above. We will rename it in the next section Φ_{GI} discuss its properties.

3.4 Geometric Integrated Information

To correct the problem arising with the stochastic interaction, we add the interaction between Y_i and Y_j :

Figure 15: The disconnected system corresponding to the geometric integrated information

The graphical model corresponding to Figure 15 is the set of disconnected distributions M_{GI} . This is not causally split in the sense that the corresponding distributions does

not satisfy the Markov properties:

$$Y_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_{I \setminus \{i\}} | X_i, \quad i \in \{1, \dots, n\}.$$

In [5] this model is called a diagonally split model and there they show in Section 3.3 that it is not causally split in a two terminal Gaussian case. We are able to see that the graphical model belonging to Figure 15 does not satisfy the Markov property above by using the definition in Section 2.3:

The moral graph of $An(X_i, X_{I \setminus \{i\}}, Y_i)$ is the fully connected graph, because every X_i is connected to a Y_i , which lies in the same chain component as every other element in $Y_{I \setminus \{i\}}$. Hence $X_{I \setminus \{i\}}$ does not separate Y_i and $X_{I \setminus \{i\}}$ and the probability distributions belonging to the graphical model do not satisfy these Markov properties in general.

Although this model does not fulfill the condition of Postulate 1, that the causal connections should be completely removed, this model satisfies the other restrictions for a complexity measure. The measure

$$\Phi_{GI} := \inf_{Q \in M_{GI}} D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q)$$

has no closed form solution, but we are able to calculate the distribution corresponding to the disconnected system with the help of an algorithm presented in the next Section.

3.4.1 Iterative Scaling Algorithm

To calculate the geometric integrated information we are able to use an iterative scaling algorithm. There are many variant forms of iterative scaling algorithms depending on the respective problem, this specific one can be solved with the help of the generalized iterative scaling algorithm introduced by Darroch and Ratcliff in [23]. Because of the similarity to the algorithm which will be presented in Section 3.6, we will take a closer look at the iterative scaling algorithm for example described by Csiszár in [22].

This will yield an algorithm that produces a sequence of probability distributions converging towards an Information projection with respect to the KL-divergence.

Convergence with respect to the KL-divergence means pointwise convergence, because of Pinsker's inequality:

Lemma 4 (Pinsker's Inequality). *Pinsker's inequality shows that the KL-divergence bounds the total variance. For probability distributions P, Q on \mathcal{Z} holds:*

$$\frac{1}{2} \| P - Q \|_1^2 \leq D(P \parallel Q)$$

Proof. The following proof is the one from Lemma 2.5 [54]. If there exists an element $z \in \mathcal{Z}$ such that $P(z) \neq 0$ and $Q(z) = 0$, then $D(P \parallel Q) = \infty$ per definition and the inequality is immediate. Now assume that there is such point. Using the function

$$\phi(x) = x \log(x) - x + 1$$

with the convention that $0 \log(0) =: 0$ leads to the observations

$$\phi(0) = 1, \phi(1) = 0, \phi'(x) = \log(x), \phi'(1) = 0, \phi''(x) = \frac{1}{x} \leq 0 \text{ and } \phi(x) \leq 0, \forall x \leq 0.$$

Additionally, the following holds

$$\left(\frac{4}{3} + \frac{2}{3}x\right) \phi(x) \leq (x-1)^2, \quad x \leq 0.$$

To prove this for $x > 0$, we look at the function

$$g(x) := (x-1)^2 - \left(\frac{4}{3} + \frac{2}{3}x\right) \phi(x).$$

This functions has the properties

$$g(1) = 0, g'(1) = 0, g''(x) = -\frac{4}{3x} \phi(x) \leq 0.$$

For ξ such that $|\xi - 1| < |x - 1|$, this leads to

$$g(x) = g(1) + g'(1)(x-1) + \frac{g''(\xi)}{2}(x-1)^2 = -\frac{4}{3\xi} \phi(\xi)(x-1)^2 \leq 0.$$

Hence, we gain that

$$\begin{aligned} \|P - Q\|_1 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} |P(z) - Q(z)| \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \left| \frac{P(z)}{Q(z)} - 1 \right| Q(z) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} Q(z) \sqrt{\left(\frac{P(z)}{Q(z)} - 1\right)^2} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} Q(z) \sqrt{\left(\frac{4}{3} + \frac{2P(z)}{3Q(z)}\right) \phi\left(\frac{P(z)}{Q(z)}\right)} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \left(\frac{4Q(z)}{3} + \frac{2P(z)}{3}\right)} \sqrt{\sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} Q(z) \phi\left(\frac{P(z)}{Q(z)}\right)} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} D(P \parallel Q)}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Figure 16: The cliques of the graphs corresponding to geometric integrated information for $n = 2$ and $n = 3$.

The desired probability distribution belongs to a graph G and therefore is a graphical model. Denote by $C(G)$ the cliques of G and $\mathcal{F}(G)$ the space of functions that factor according to the cliques as in Definition 23. Take $\{f_1, \dots, f_s\}$, $s \in \mathbb{N}$ as a basis of $\mathcal{F}(G)$ then we are able to define the manifold of distributions belonging to the disconnected model as

$$M_{GI} = \left\{ P(z) = \frac{e^{\sum_{j=1}^s \lambda_j f_j(z)}}{\sum_{z' \in \mathcal{Z}} e^{\sum_{j=1}^s \lambda_j f_j(z')}} \mid \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^s, z \in \mathcal{Z} \right\}.$$

Now P^0 be the distribution of the full system. Using the vectors $f_j \in \mathcal{F}(G)$ from the basis above and

$$k_j := \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P^0(z) f_j(z)$$

leads to the definition of a linear family

$$L(\mathcal{F}, k) := \left\{ P \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \mid \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) f_j(z) = k_j, j \in \{1, \dots, s\} \right\}. \quad (34)$$

This fixes the values on the cliques as displayed in Figure 16.

Now we are able to use the following Lemma, which is the result of the duality of the exponential and mixture families described in Section 2.2:

Lemma 5. *The following properties are equivalent for any distribution $\hat{P} \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$, with \overline{M}_{GI} as the closure of M_{GI} :*

- (1) $\hat{P} \in L(\mathcal{F}, k) \cap \overline{M}_{GI}$.
- (2) $\hat{P} = \arg \inf_{P \in \overline{M}_{GI}} D(Q \parallel P)$, for all $Q \in L(\mathcal{F}, k)$.

$$(3) \hat{P} = \arg \inf_{Q \in L(\mathcal{F}, k)} D(Q \| P), \text{ for all } P \in \overline{M}_{GI}.$$

Additionally, there exists a unique distribution satisfying the statements above.

Proof. See Theorem 2.8 in [7]. □

Hence we are able to use an algorithm that minimizes the KL-divergence with respect to the first argument from $L(\mathcal{F}, k)$ in order to gain a distribution that minimizes the KL-divergence with respect to the second argument from \overline{M}_{GI} .

Theorem 3.1 (The GIS algorithm, [23]). *Let $P^{(0)}(x)$ be the uniform distribution, $f_j \in \mathcal{F}(G)$ a basis vector and*

$$P^{(m)}(z) = P^{(m-1)}(z) \prod_{i=j}^s \left(\frac{k_j}{\sum_{z' \in \mathcal{Z}} P^{(m-1)}(z') f_j(z')} \right)^{f_j(z)}$$

with $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Then the $P^{(m)}$ converge to the unique solution $P^* \in \overline{M}_{GI}$ that minimizes the KL-divergence from $L(\mathcal{F}, k)$ with respect to the first variable.

Csiszár describes in [18] a geometric interpretation of this algorithm and proves the convergence using the following iterative scaling algorithm. For the next one, we restrict the sets $L(\mathcal{F}, k)$ to sets in which the certain marginals are fixed:

$$\mathcal{L} = \{P \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \mid P(z_j) = k_j, \quad j \in \{1, \dots, s\}\}. \quad (35)$$

It is easy to perform an i-projection onto this family by scaling

$$P'(z_j) = \frac{k_j}{\sum_{z'_j \in \mathcal{Z}_j} P(z'_j)} P(z_j), \quad z_j \in \mathcal{Z}_j \quad (36)$$

see [16] in the beginning of Section 5.1 . This leads to the following less general iterative scaling algorithm.

Theorem 3.2 (The Iterative Scaling algorithm, [20], [22]). *Let $\mathcal{L}_1, \dots, \mathcal{L}_t$, $t \in \mathbb{N}$ be linear sets of the form (35) with a non-empty intersection \mathcal{L} and $P \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$ with $S(P) = \mathcal{Z}$. Now define $P^{(m+1)}$ as the information projection of $P^{(m)}$ to \mathcal{L}_i , $i = m \bmod t$. Then this cyclic iteration converges to P^* , the I-projection of P on \mathcal{L} .*

Proof. The proof is the one of Theorem 5.1 in [22]. With the generalized Pythagorean theorem, Theorem 2.1, for every $P \in \mathcal{L}$ the equality

$$D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^{m-1}) = D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^m) + D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P^m \parallel P^{m-1}), \quad m = 1, 2, \dots$$

holds. Using this inductively leads to

$$D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^0) = D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^M) + \sum_{m=1}^M D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P^m \parallel P^{m-1}), \quad M \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (37)$$

Because of the compactness of $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$ there exists a subsequence $P^{m_k} \rightarrow P'$ for $m_k \rightarrow \infty$. Substituting M_k for M in (37) leads to

$$D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^0) = D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^{M_k}) + \sum_{m=1}^{M_k} D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P^m \parallel P^{m-1}), \quad M \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Now we send M_k to infinity in the equality above to gain

$$D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^0) = D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P') + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P^m \parallel P^{m-1}). \quad (38)$$

The sequence P^{m_k} converges and with that the terms $D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P^m \parallel P^{m-1})$, $m \leq m_k$ go to 0. Using Pinsker's inequality from Lemma 4 yields

$$P^{M_k+1} \rightarrow P', \quad P^{M_k+2} \rightarrow P', \dots, P^{M_k+m-1} \rightarrow P'.$$

We now gain that $P' \in \bigcap_{i=1}^m \mathcal{L}_i$, because every \mathcal{L}_i is closed. Therefore we are able to substitute P' for P in (38)

$$D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P' \parallel P^0) = D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P' \parallel P') + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P^m \parallel P^{m-1}) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P^m \parallel P^{m-1}).$$

Now substituting this again in (38) leads to

$$D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^0) = D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P') + D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P' \parallel P^0).$$

Hence P' is the information projection, meaning the minimization of the KL-divergence with respect to the first variable, of P^0 to \mathcal{L} . Since P^{m_k} is an arbitrary convergent subsequence, every convergent subsequence converges towards P' and with that and the compactness we gain $P^m \rightarrow P'$ for $m \rightarrow \infty$. \square

Hence, we are able to calculate the distribution belonging to the disconnected system and therefore it is possible to calculate the complexity measure belonging to the geometric integrated information. The problem that this model does not satisfy Postulate 2 leads to the following additional approach.

3.5 Common Exterior Influence

In the last two sections we saw, that removing the connection between the Y_i 's leads to problems as well as including these connections fully. The following approach is a new one that only includes common exterior influences on the Y_i 's and not direct interactions. This leads to the graphs in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Disconnected models with exterior influences for $n = 2$ and $n = 4$.

The moral graph of $An(X_1, X_2, Y_1) = \{X_1, X_2, Y_1, W\}$ is displayed in Figure 18 and we see that X_1 still separates $X_{I \setminus \{1\}}$ from Y_1 . The distributions of the graphical model belonging to these chain graphs therefore satisfy Postulate 1.

Figure 18: Moral graph $An(X_1, X_2, Y_1)$.

Let M_{CEI} be the graphical model belonging to the disconnected graph discussed above. Therefore we need to include W in our notation in the following way. For this section, we define $Z := (X, W, Y)$ and the sample set $\mathcal{Z} = \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{W} \times \mathcal{Y}$. This leads to the measure

$$\Phi_{CEI} := \inf_{Q \in M_{CEI}} D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q).$$

Now we are going to compare the graphical model of the disconnected system defined here to the one defined by the disconnected system of geometric integrated information

M_{GI} . We saw in the last section, that geometric integrated information does not satisfy Postulate 1 in general. Considering that the model presented here satisfies Postulate 1 leads to the conclusion that

$$M_{GI} \not\subseteq M_{CEI}.$$

To analyze the other direction we will look closely at the distributions in M_{CEI} . Let $P \in M_{CEI}$. Considering the definition of a graphical model and the factorization for chain graphs corresponding to the chain-graph Markov properties, there exist functions f_1, f_2, f_3 and g_1, g_2, g_3 corresponding to the cliques consisting of

$$\{X_1, Y_1\}, \{Y_1, W\}, \{X_1, Y_1, W\}, \{X_2, Y_2\}, \{Y_2, W\} \text{ and } \{X_2, Y_2, W\}$$

such that we are able to write

$$\begin{aligned} P(y_1|x_1, w) &= f_1(w, y_1)f_2(x_1, y_1)f_3(x_1, y_1, w) \\ P(y_2|x_2, w) &= g_1(w, y_2)g_2(x_2, y_2)g_3(x_2, y_2, w) \\ P(z) &= P(x_1, x_2)P(y_1|x_1, w)P(y_2|x_2, w)P(w). \end{aligned}$$

Now marginalizing with respect to W leads to:

$$\begin{aligned} P(x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2) &= \sum_{w \in W} P(x_1, x_2)P(y_1|x_1, w)P(y_2|x_2, w)P(w) \\ &= P(x_1, x_2)f_2(x_1, y_1)g_2(x_2, y_2) \sum_{w \in W} P(w)f_1(w, y_1)f_3(x_1, y_1, w)g_1(w, y_2)g_3(x_2, y_2, w). \end{aligned}$$

By defining $\phi(x_1, y_1, y_1, y_2) := \sum_{w \in W} P(w)f_1(w, y_1)f_3(x_1, y_1, w)g_1(w, y_2)g_3(x_2, y_2, w)$ we gain the following form:

$$P(x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2) = P(x_1, x_2)f_2(x_1, y_1)g_2(x_2, y_2)\phi(x_1, y_1, y_1, y_2).$$

This would be the parametrization of a distribution belonging to the graphical model M_{GI} if ϕ would only depend on Y_1, Y_2 . But in general it does and therefore we have

$$M_{CEI} \not\subseteq M_{GI}.$$

This has to be further analyzed.

3.6 Integrated Information

This approach is called the ‘‘Causally split model’’ in [5] and ‘‘Integrated Information’’ in [37]. We can describe the conditions for the disconnected model as follows:

$$M_G := \{Q \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \mid Q(Y_i \mid X) = Q(Y_i \mid X_i), \text{ for all } i \in \{1, \dots, n\}\}. \quad (39)$$

This leads to the complexity measure

$$\Phi_G := \inf_{Q \in M_G} D(P \parallel Q).$$

The distributions in M_G do not belong to a graphical model any more. One can see that by imagining edges between the Y 's. This would lead to the model of Geometric Integrated Information which does not necessarily satisfies the independence property defined in (39). Removing these edges would result in the model belonging to stochastic interaction, which does not satisfy Postulate 1 in general in contrast to this one, see [37]. Therefore we need different methods to analyze the structure of this kind of model.

We are able to write the requirements to the distributions in (39) as conditional independent statements. In the case of $n = 2$ the conditions for the disconnected model correspond to:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_1 &\perp\!\!\!\perp X_2 \mid X_1 \\ Y_2 &\perp\!\!\!\perp X_1 \mid X_2 \end{aligned}$$

and in general we have

$$Y_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid X_i.$$

There is no analytically closed way to calculate this value in general. In the supporting information of [37] in the section ‘‘Integrated Information for Gaussian Variables’’ and in [36] one can see that it is possible to gain a closed formula under the restrictions that the probability distributions are Gaussian distributions.

Using the method from algebraic statistics introduced in section 2.4, we can attempt to analyze the primary decomposition over \mathbb{Q} in the case of $n = 2$ and binary variables on $\mathcal{Z} = \{1, 2\}$. Considering $Y_1 = Z_3, Y_2 = Z_4$ leads to the Macaulay2 program

```

loadPackage "GraphicalModels"
S = markovRing(2,2,2,2)
L = {{{3},{2},{1}}, {{4},{1},{2}}}
I = conditionalIndependenceIdeal(S,L)
K = primaryDecomposition I

```

This yields a decomposition of $I_{Z_3 \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_2 | Z_1} + I_{Z_4 \perp\!\!\!\perp Z_1 | Z_2}$ in two different ideals. Here we will denote the marginals in the following way

$$P(x_1, x_2) = \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} P(x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2) =: P(x_1, x_2, +, +)$$

The first ideal is the one generated by the X -marginals

$$I_{P(X)} := \langle P(2, 2, +, +), P(2, 1, +, +), P(1, 2, +, +), P(1, 1, +, +) \rangle.$$

Hence the variety of this ideal consists of distributions on the boundary of $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$. To be able to look at the generators of the second Ideal more closely, one can use the following additional line

netList $K\#0_*$

to gain that the second Ideal has five generators:

$$1 \quad P(2, 1, 2, +)P(2, 2, 1, +) - P(2, 1, 1, +)P(2, 2, 2, +)$$

$$2 \quad P(1, 2, +, 2)P(2, 2, +, 1) - P(1, 2, +, 1)P(2, 2, +, 2)$$

$$3 \quad P(1, 1, +, 2)P(2, 1, +, 1) - P(1, 1, +, 1)P(2, 1, +, 2)$$

$$4 \quad P(1, 1, 2, +)P(1, 2, 1, +) - P(1, 1, 1, +)P(1, 2, 2, +)$$

5 The last generator needs longer careful calculations to gain

$$\begin{aligned} & P(1, 1, +, 2)P(1, 2, 2, +)P(2, 1, 2, +)P(2, 2, +, 2) \\ & - P(1, 1, 2, +)P(1, 2, +, 2)P(2, 1, +, 2)P(2, 2, 2, +) \end{aligned}$$

This encodes the independence structure of the Ideal. Therefore we were not able to divide this conditional independence ideal in significant smaller ones, but in one belonging to the distributions on \mathcal{X} and one that holds the structure of this ideal.

We are able to look at the conditional independence statements independently by defining

$$S_i := \{Q \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \mid Q(Y_i \mid X) = Q(Y_i \mid X_i)\}. \quad (40)$$

Using this we have $M_G = \bigcap_{i=1}^n S_i$. Therefore each S_i corresponds to one conditional independence statement

$$Y_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid X_i.$$

Then the definition in (40) is equivalent to

$$S_i := \{Q \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \mid Q(Y_i, X_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid X_i) = Q(Y_i \mid X_i) \cdot Q(X_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid X_i)\} \quad (41)$$

because of the equalities

$$Q(y_i \mid x_i) = \frac{Q(y_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i)}{Q(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i)} = Q(y_i \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}) = Q(y_i \mid x)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} Q(y_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i) &= \frac{Q(y_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, x_i)}{Q(x_i)} \\ &= \frac{Q(y_i \mid x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, x_i) \cdot Q(x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, x_i)}{Q(x_i)} \\ &= Q(y_i \mid x_i) \cdot Q(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i) \end{aligned}$$

for all $z \in \mathcal{Z}$.

In the supporting information of [37] they show in the case of $n = 2$ and binary units that X -marginals of the information projection P^* of P^0 to M_G are equal to the X -marginals of P^0 , by introducing Lagrange multipliers. This leads to the idea of fixing the values on \mathcal{X} initially

$$\tilde{S}_i(P^0) = \{Q \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}) \mid Q \in S_i \text{ and } Q(x) = P^0(x) \forall x \in \mathcal{X}\}$$

and to the result.

Lemma 6. *Let P^0 be the distribution of the full system, $\tilde{S}_i(P^0)$ and $\tilde{M}_G = \bigcap_{i=1}^n \tilde{S}_i(P^0)$, then all $\tilde{S}_i(P^0)$ are convex sets. Hence \tilde{M}_G is also a convex set.*

Proof. Let $P, Q \in \tilde{S}_i(P^0)$, $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and $\lambda \in [0, 1]$. Then we have for all $z \in \mathcal{Z}$ and

$$P_\lambda(z) := \lambda P(z) + (1 - \lambda)Q(z)$$

that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\lambda(y_i, x) &= \lambda P(y_i|x_i)P(x) + (1 - \lambda)Q(y_i|x_i)Q(x) \\ P_\lambda(y_i|x) &= \frac{\lambda P(y_i|x_i)P(x) + (1 - \lambda)Q(y_i|x_i)Q(x)}{\lambda P(x) + (1 - \lambda)Q(x)} \\ &= \frac{\lambda P(y_i|x_i)P(x) + (1 - \lambda)Q(y_i|x_i)Q(x)}{P(x)} \\ &= \lambda P(y_i|x_i) + (1 - \lambda)Q(y_i|x_i) \\ P_\lambda(y_i|x_i) &= \frac{\lambda P(y_i, x_i) + (1 - \lambda)Q(y_i, x_i)}{\lambda P(x_i) + (1 - \lambda)Q(x_i)} \\ &= \lambda P(y_i|x_i) + (1 - \lambda)Q(y_i|x_i) \end{aligned}$$

and therefore $P_\lambda \in \tilde{S}_i(P^0)$. □

Now the following holds for \tilde{M}_G .

Lemma 7. *Let $S \subseteq \mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$ be a closed convex set and $Q \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$, $Q \neq S$. Then $P^* \in S$ exists such that it is the I-projection from Q to S and the following holds*

$$D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q) \geq D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^*) + D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P^* \parallel Q).$$

Proof. The existence of the I-projections follows from the convexity of the KL-divergence in Theorem 2.7.2 [16] and the rest from [16] Theorem 11.6.1. \square

This provides us with a unique I-projection in the case that the X -marginals are fixed. In [21] one can find a similar result for the rI-projection, but a log-convex set is needed for this. A set $S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots\}$ is log-convex if $\log S := \{\log s_1, \log s_2, \dots\}$ is convex. Unfortunately, this does not hold for \tilde{S}_i or S_i as one can see in the following easy example. Lets consider binary variables and $n = 2$. Let P^1 be the uniform distribution and P^2 be

X_1	X_2	Y_1	Y_2	P^2
0	0	0	0	0.0125
0	0	0	1	0.0125
0	0	1	0	0.1125
0	0	1	1	0.1125
0	1	0	0	0.0125
0	1	0	1	0.0125
0	1	1	0	0.1125
0	1	1	1	0.1125
1	0	0	0	0.0625
1	0	0	1	0.0625
1	0	1	0	0.0625
1	0	1	1	0.0625
1	1	0	0	0.0625
1	1	0	1	0.0625
1	1	1	0	0.0625
1	1	1	1	0.0625

this satisfies the conditional independence statement $Y_1 \perp\!\!\!\perp X_2 | X_1$ and is uniformly distributed on \mathcal{X} . This leads for $\lambda = 0.5$ to

$$P_\lambda(y_1 = 0, x = (0, 1)) = 0.5 \cdot \log_2(0.125) + 0.5 \cdot \log_2(0.025)$$

$$P_\lambda(x = (0, 1)) = \log_2(0.25)$$

$$P_\lambda(y_1 = 0, x_1 = 0) = 0.5 \cdot \log_2(0.25) + 0.5 \cdot \log_2(0.05)$$

$$P_\lambda(x = 0) = \log_2(0.5)$$

and with that $P_\lambda(y_1 = 0|x = (0, 1)) \approx 2.0805 \neq 3.1610 \approx P_\lambda(y_1 = 0|x_1 = 0)$.

We are able to define and proof a rI-projection from an arbitrary probability distribution P to one S_i .

Lemma 8. *Let $P \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$ with positive marginals on X then P^* defined as*

$$P^*(z) := P^*(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i) \cdot P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i) \quad (42)$$

$$P^*(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i) := \frac{P(x_i, y_i) \cdot P(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}})}{P(x_i)} \quad (43)$$

is for all $z \in \mathcal{Z}$ an rI-projection from P to S_i . Furthermore P^* is the uniquely defined rI-projection.

Before proving this Lemma, we will state some useful properties of P^* .

Property 1. $P(x_i, y_i) = P^*(x_i, y_i)$, for all $x_i \in \mathcal{X}_i$, $y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i$.

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} P(x_i, y_i) &= P(x_i, y_i) \cdot \frac{P(x_i)}{P(x_i)} \\ &= \frac{P(x_i, y_i)}{P(x_i)} \sum_{x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \in \mathcal{X}_{I \setminus \{i\}}} P(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}) \\ &= \sum_{x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \in \mathcal{X}_{I \setminus \{i\}}} P^*(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i) \\ &= P^*(x_i, y_i), \quad \text{for all } x_i \in \mathcal{X}_i, y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i. \end{aligned}$$

□

Property 2. $P(x_i) = P^*(x_i)$, for all $x_i \in \mathcal{X}_i$.

Proof. Sum over all $y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i$ in Property 1.

□

Property 3. $P(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i) = P^*(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i)$, for all $x_i \in \mathcal{X}_i$, $x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \in \mathcal{X}_{I \setminus \{i\}}$.

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i) &= \frac{P^*(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}})}{P^*(x_i)} \\
&= \frac{1}{P^*(x_i)} \sum_{y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i} P^*(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i) \\
&= \frac{1}{P^*(x_i)} \sum_{y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i} \frac{P(x_i, y_i) \cdot P(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}})}{P(x_i)} \\
&= \frac{1}{P^*(x_i)} \cdot P(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i) \sum_{y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i} P(x_i, y_i) \\
&= \frac{1}{P^*(x_i)} \cdot P(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i) \sum_{y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i} P^*(x_i, y_i) \\
&= P(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i)
\end{aligned}$$

□

Property 4. $P(x) = P^*(x)$, for all $x \in \mathcal{X}$.

Proof. Using Property 2 and 3 we gain:

$$P(x) = P(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i) \cdot P(x_i) = P^*(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i) \cdot P^*(x_i) = P^*(x).$$

□

In Property 4 we see that the marginal distribution $P^*(X)$ stays fixed to the marginal of the initial distribution $P(X)$.

Proof of Lemma 8. Straightforward calculations show that $P^* \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$. At first, we show that $P \in S_i$ by using the definition in (41)

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(y_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i) &= \frac{P^*(y_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, x_i)}{P^*(x_i)} \\
&= \frac{P(x_i, y_i)P(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}})}{P(x_i)P(x_i)} \\
&= P^*(y_i | x_i)P^*(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i) \quad \text{for all } z \in \mathcal{Z}.
\end{aligned}$$

The last equality holds due to the Properties 1, 2 and 3 and with this we gain that $P^* \in S_i$.

It remains to show, that $D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^*) \leq D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q)$ for all $Q \in S_i$. Now take an arbitrary $Q \in S_i$.

If $D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q) \leq D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^*)$ holds, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^*) - D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q) \\
&= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log \frac{P(z)}{P^*(z)} - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log \frac{P(z)}{Q(z)} \\
&= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log Q(z) - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log P^*(z). \tag{44}
\end{aligned}$$

With (40) we get for all $z \in \mathcal{Z}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(z) &= P^*(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i) \cdot P^*(y_i \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}) \cdot P^*(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}) \\
&= P^*(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i) \cdot P^*(y_i, x_i) \cdot P^*(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i), \\
Q(z) &= Q(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i) \cdot Q(y_i, x_i) \cdot Q(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i).
\end{aligned}$$

Substituting these into (44) leads to:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log Q(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i) \cdot Q(y_i, x_i) \cdot Q(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i) \\
& \quad - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log P^*(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i) \cdot P^*(y_i, x_i) \cdot P^*(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i) \\
&= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log \frac{Q(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i)}{P^*(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i)} + \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log Q(y_i, x_i) \\
& \quad + \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log Q(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i) - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log P(y_i, x_i) - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log P(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i) \\
&= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log \frac{Q(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i)}{P^*(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i)} + \sum_{\substack{x_i \in \mathcal{X}_i, \\ y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i}} P(x_i, y_i) \log Q(y_i, x_i) \\
& \quad + \sum_{\substack{x_i \in \mathcal{X}_i, \\ x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \in \mathcal{X}_{I \setminus \{i\}}}} P(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}) \log Q(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i) + H_P(Y_i, X_i) + H_P(X_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid X_i)
\end{aligned}$$

By using Proposition 5 we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
& D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^*) - D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q) \\
&= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log \frac{Q(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i)}{P^*(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i)} - D_{\mathcal{X}_i, \mathcal{Y}_i}(P \parallel Q) - D_{\mathcal{X}_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid X_i}(P \parallel Q).
\end{aligned}$$

The definition of P^* holds the additional property that:

$$\begin{aligned}
P^*(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i) &= \frac{P^*(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}, x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i)}{P^*(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i)} \\
&= \frac{P^*(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i) \cdot P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i)}{P^*(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i)} \\
&= P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i)
\end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

Finally, we get that

$$D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel P^*) - D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P \parallel Q) = -D_{\mathcal{Y}_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}_i}(P \parallel Q) - D_{\mathcal{X}_i, \mathcal{Y}_i}(P \parallel Q) - D_{\mathcal{X}_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid \mathcal{X}_i}(P \parallel Q).$$

Proposition 5 shows, that all of these joint and conditional KL-Divergences are non-negative. Therefore all of them have to be zero:

$$0 = D_{\mathcal{Y}_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}_i}(P \parallel Q) = D_{\mathcal{X}_i, \mathcal{Y}_i}(P \parallel Q) = D_{\mathcal{X}_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid \mathcal{X}_i}(P \parallel Q).$$

This provides us with the result that P^* is an information projection to S_i . In order to gain the uniqueness of this projection, we will take a closer look at these vanishing KL-Divergences. We know from the Propositions 5 and 3 that the KL-Divergences equal 0 if and only if the distributions are the same. This leads to the following three properties of Q :

- (1) $Q(X_i, Y_i) = P(X_i, Y_i)$
- (2) $Q(X_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid X_i) = P(X_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid X_i)$
- (3) $Q(Y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid X_{I \setminus \{i\}}, X_i, Y_i) = P(Y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid X, Y_i)$

With (45), Property 1 and 3 all of these equalities hold also for P^* instead of P . Finally this leads to

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{P^*(z) \cdot P(x_i)}{P(x_i, y_i) \cdot P(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}})} &= \frac{P^*(z)}{P^*(x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, x_i, y_i)} \\
&= P^*(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, x_i, y_i) \\
&= Q(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} \mid x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, x_i, y_i) \\
&= \frac{Q(z)}{Q(x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, x_i, y_i)} \\
&= \frac{Q(z) \cdot P(x_i)}{P(x_i, y_i) \cdot P(x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}})}
\end{aligned}$$

and therefore to $P^*(z) = Q(z)$ for all $z \in \mathcal{Z}$. □

We are able to write for every $P \in S_i$

$$P(z) = P(y_i|x_i)P(x) \cdot P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}|y_i, x).$$

Considering only the first part and pretending that $Y_{I \setminus \{i\}}$ does not exist would lead to an exponential family, while second part $P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}|y_i, x)$ has a different structure. This is the reason why we will define another divergence that is modified with respect to these observations. Now minimizing the following divergence results in performing an rI-projection with respect to the part that looks like an exponential family and an I-projection with respect to the other part.

Definition 28 (Modified KL-Divergence). For $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ we define

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{D}_i(P \parallel Q) &:= D_{\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}_i}(P \parallel Q) + D_{\mathcal{Y}_{I \setminus \{i\}} | \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}_i}(Q \parallel P) \\ &= D_{\mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) + D_{\mathcal{Y}_i | \mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) + D_{\mathcal{Y}_{I \setminus \{i\}} | \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}_i}(Q \parallel P). \end{aligned}$$

This newly defined divergence has some useful properties.

Proposition 14 (Properties of the Modified KL-Divergence). *Let $P, Q \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$. For $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ the following properties hold for every \tilde{D}_i :*

(i) $\tilde{D}_i(P \parallel Q) \geq 0$ and $\tilde{D}_i(P \parallel Q) = 0$ if and only if $P = Q$.

(ii) If P is the projection of Q to S_i , then

$$\tilde{D}_i(Q \parallel P) = D(Q \parallel P).$$

(iii) If P^* is the projection of P to S_i with respect to the KL-divergence, then it also minimized the modified KL-divergence

$$\tilde{D}_i(P \parallel P^*) \leq \tilde{D}_i(P \parallel Q), \quad \forall Q \in S_i.$$

Proof. The properties in (i) follow directly from the properties of the KL-divergence in Proposition 3 and the fact that we can write \tilde{D}_i as

$$\tilde{D}_i(P \parallel Q) = D_{\mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) + D_{\mathcal{Y}_i | \mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) + D_{\mathcal{Y}_{I \setminus \{i\}} | \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}_i}(Q \parallel P).$$

For (ii) we use Property 2 and (45)

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{D}_i(P \parallel Q) &= D_{\mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) + D_{\mathcal{Y}_i | \mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) + D_{\mathcal{Y}_{I \setminus \{i\}} | \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}_i}(Q \parallel P) \\ &= D_{\mathcal{Y}_i | \mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) \\ &= D_{\mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) + D_{\mathcal{Y}_i | \mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) + D_{\mathcal{Y}_{I \setminus \{i\}} | \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}_i}(P \parallel Q) \\ &= D(P \parallel Q). \end{aligned}$$

The proof of (iii) is very similar to the one of Lemma 8.

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \tilde{D}_i(P \parallel P^*) - \tilde{D}_i(P \parallel Q) \\
&= \sum_{\substack{x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i}} P(x, y_i) \log \frac{P(x, y_i)}{P^*(x, y_i)} + \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P^*(z) \log \frac{P^*(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x, y_i)}{P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x, y_i)} \\
&\quad - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P(x) \log \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} - \sum_{\substack{x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i}} P(x, y_i) \log \frac{P(x, y_i)}{Q(x, y_i)} - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} Q(z) \log \frac{Q(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x, y_i)}{P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x, y_i)} \\
&= \sum_{\substack{x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i}} P(x, y_i) \log \frac{Q(x, y_i)}{P^*(x, y_i)} - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P(x) \log \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} Q(z) \log \frac{Q(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x, y_i)}{P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x, y_i)} \\
&= \sum_{\substack{x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i}} P(x, y_i) \log \frac{Q(y_i | x_i)}{P(y_i | x_i)} - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P(x) \log \frac{P(x)}{Q(x)} - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} Q(z) \log \frac{Q(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x, y_i)}{P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x, y_i)} \\
&= -D_{\mathcal{Y}_i | \mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) - D_{\mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) - D_{\mathcal{Y}_{I \setminus \{i\}} | \mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}_i}(Q \parallel P)
\end{aligned}$$

Proposition 5 shows, that all of these joint and conditional KL-Divergences are non-negative. Therefore all of them have to be zero

$$0 = D_{\mathcal{Y}_{I \setminus \{i\}} | \mathcal{Y}_i, \mathcal{X}}(P \parallel Q) = D_{\mathcal{X}_{I \setminus \{i\}}, \mathcal{Y}_{I \setminus \{i\}}}(P \parallel Q) = D_{\mathcal{X}_{I \setminus \{i\}} | \mathcal{X}_i}(P \parallel Q).$$

This provides us with the result, that P^* is the Information Projection to S_i with respect to the second argument and the modified KL-divergence. Similar to the proof of Lemma 8 we then gain that $P^*(z) = Q(z)$ for all $z \in \mathcal{Z}$. \square

This modified KL-divergence allows the definition of a new generalized Pythagorean theorem.

Figure 19: Sketch of a generalized Pythagorean triangle with respect to the modified KL-divergence

Lemma 9 (Generalized Pythagorean Theorem for the Modified KL-Divergence). *For $P^m, P \in S_i, P \neq P^m$ and P^m as the rI-Projection of P^{m-1} to S_i the following holds:*

$$\tilde{D}_i(P^{m-1} \parallel P) = \tilde{D}_i(P^{m-1} \parallel P^m) + \tilde{D}_i(P^m \parallel P)$$

Proof. Using the properties the rI-projection shown earlier in this section, we gain the relation with the following calculation.

$$\begin{aligned} & \tilde{D}_i(P^{m-1} \parallel P) + \tilde{D}_i(P^m \parallel P) \\ &= \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P^{m-1}(x) \log \frac{P^{m-1}(x)}{P^m(x)} + \sum_{\substack{x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i}} P^{m-1}(x, y_i) \log \frac{P^{m-1}(y_i|x)}{P^m(y_i|x)} \\ & \quad + \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P^m(z) \log \frac{P^m(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}|y_i, x)}{P^{m-1}(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}|y_i, x)} + \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P^m(x) \log \frac{P^m(x)}{P(x)} \\ & \quad + \sum_{\substack{x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i}} P^m(x, y_i) \log \frac{P^m(y_i|x)}{P(y_i|x)} + \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log \frac{P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}|y_i, x)}{P^m(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}|y_i, x)} \\ &= \sum_{\substack{x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i}} P^{m-1}(x, y_i) \log \frac{P^{m-1}(y_i|x)}{P^m(y_i|x)} + \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P^m(x) \log \frac{P^m(x)}{P(x)} \\ & \quad + \sum_{\substack{x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i}} P^m(x, y_i) \log \frac{P^m(y_i|x)}{P(y_i|x)} + \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log \frac{P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}|y_i, x)}{P^m(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}|y_i, x)} \\ &= \sum_{\substack{x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i}} P^{m-1}(x, y_i) \log \frac{P^{m-1}(y_i|x)}{P^m(y_i|x)} + \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P^{m-1}(x) \log \frac{P^{m-1}(x)}{P(x)} \\ & \quad + \sum_{\substack{x_i \in \mathcal{X}_i, \\ y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i}} P^m(x_i, y_i) \log \frac{P^m(y_i|x_i)}{P(y_i|x_i)} + \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log \frac{P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}|y_i, x)}{P^{m-1}(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}|y_i, x)} \\ &= \sum_{\substack{x \in \mathcal{X}, \\ y_i \in \mathcal{Y}_i}} P^{m-1}(x, y_i) \log \frac{P^{m-1}(y_i|x)}{P(y_i|x)} + \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P^{m-1}(x) \log \frac{P^{m-1}(x)}{P(x)} \\ & \quad + \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P(z) \log \frac{P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}|y_i, x)}{P^{m-1}(y_{I \setminus \{i\}}|y_i, x)} \\ &= \tilde{D}_i(P^{m-1} \parallel P) \end{aligned}$$

□

3.6.1 Modified Iterative Scaling Algorithm

As we have seen in Section 3.4.1, one core concept of iterative scaling is the division of the desired properties into parts, which define families of probability distributions that satisfy a part of the requirements. The iterative scaling algorithm works by performing an I-projection to one of these parts and then iterating through them cyclically.

We are able to apply the same idea to M_G . The natural way of dividing M_G is by using the S_i examined in the last section: $M_G = \bigcap_i S_i$. In the last section in Lemma 8 we additionally proved that there exists a unique rI-projection P^* from an arbitrary $P \in \mathcal{P}^o(\mathcal{Z})$ to a S_i and that this is of the form

$$P^*(z) = P(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i) P(x_i, y_i) P(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i).$$

Now this leads to the following algorithm:

Definition 29. Let $P^0 \in \mathcal{Z}$ be a probability distribution with $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \text{supp}(P^0)$. Then we define one step of the algorithm as projection to S_i as:

$$P^m(z) = P^{m-1}(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i) P^{m-1}(x_i, y_i) P^{m-1}(y_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i, x_{I \setminus \{i\}}, y_i), \quad i = m \bmod n$$

for all $z \in \mathcal{Z}$ and $m \in \mathbb{N}$.

The idea of this algorithm is displayed in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Sketch of the idea of the algorithm from Definition 29

We are able to rewrite the elements of the sequence $\{P^m\}_{m \in \mathbb{N}}$, defined by the algorithm above, as

$$\begin{aligned} P^m(z) &= \frac{P(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i)}{P^{m-1}(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i, y_i)} P^{m-1}(z) \\ &= P^0(z) \prod_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{P(x_{I \setminus \{i_k\}} | x_{i_k})}{P^k(x_{I \setminus \{i_k\}} | x_{i_k}, y_{i_k})} \quad \text{with } i_k = (k \bmod n) + 1. \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

This leads to the following result

Proposition 15. *If the algorithm from Definition 29 converges to an element P^* in the way that there exists a $M \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $D(P^m \parallel P^{m+1}) = 0$ for $m \geq M$, then $P^* \in M_G$.*

Proof. Considering (46) this is easy to see, because then we have for every $i \in I$

$$\frac{P^*(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i)}{P^*(x_{I \setminus \{i\}} | x_i, y_i)}, \quad \text{for all } z \in \mathcal{Z} = \frac{P^*(y_i | x_i)}{P^*(y_i | x)} = 1, \quad \text{for all } z \in \mathcal{Z}$$

and therefore $P^*(Y_i | X_i) = P^*(Y_i | X)$. \square

Additionally, this sequence holds the following property.

Lemma 10. *The KL-divergences of the sequence P^m, P^{m+1}, \dots as in Definition 29, meaning $D(P^m \parallel P^{m+1})$, is bounded from below by 0 and from above by a constant k_P that depends on the initial distribution P .*

Proof. The lower bound follows directly from the non-negativity of the KL-divergence 3. To gain the upper bound we can write:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\mathcal{Z}}(P^m \parallel P^{m+1}) &= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P^m(z) \log \frac{P^m(z)}{P^{m+1}(z)} \\ &= \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P^m(z) \log \frac{P^m(z) P^m(x_j) P^m(x_j, y_j, x_{I \setminus \{j\}})}{P^m(x_j, y_j) P^m(x_j, x_{I \setminus \{j\}}) P^m(z)} \\ &= -H_{P^m}(Y_j | X_{I \setminus \{j\}} X_j) - \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} P^m(z) \log P^m(x_{I \setminus \{j\}} | x_j) \\ &\leq - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P^m(x) \log P^m(x_{I \setminus \{j\}} | x_j) \\ &= - \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P(x) \log P(x_{I \setminus \{j\}} | x_j). \end{aligned}$$

The last equality holds because of Property 4. Now we can define the constant

$$k_P := \max_{j \in \{1, \dots, n\}} \sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P(x) \log \frac{1}{P(x_{I \setminus \{j\}} | x_j)}$$

and this only depends on the initial distribution. \square

(a) Figure published in [37]

(b) Comparison with Φ_G generated by the modified algorithm.

Figure 21: Comparison of different complexity measures: mutual information (black), sum of transfer entropies (green), transfer entropy (blue and dotted blue) and integrated information (red).

Although this does not prove the convergence of this algorithm, the properties above combined with the Pythagorean theorem for the modified KL-divergence might be important steps towards a proof of convergence. Additionally, tests with two different implementations always converged up to this point.

Despite the natural arising of the S_i and the strong connection to iterative scaling, this algorithm does not converge towards the distribution with the minimal divergence in general. In [37] Oizumi et al. computed Φ_G for an easy example by using Lagrange multipliers and the Newton method, see supporting information of [37] for details. The example is the one already mentioned in Section 3.7. There we have $n = 2$ and binary nodes that at first behave in the following way

X_1	X_2	Y_1	Y_2
0	0	0	0
0	1	0	0
1	0	0	0
1	1	1	1

with uniformly distributed X_1 and X_2 . Then some noise gets added to Y_2 . We were able to reproduce the results published in [37] regarding the mutual information, the sum of transfer entropies and the individual transfer entropies. The results produced by the algorithm presented here were calculated with an implementation in Julia done

by Dr. Virgo and one in C++ implemented by me and differ from the true result by approx. 0.1. This is displayed in Figure 21(b) done by Dr. Virgo. The distribution resulting from our algorithm satisfies the conditional independence statements, therefore lies on the manifold M_G , but is not the one minimizing the distance.

Another problem with this algorithm might result from its definition. Once the first step is done, the algorithm does not need the initial distribution any more whereas the iterative scaling algorithm uses the constraints defined by the initial distribution in each step. This might lead to numerical errors that can build up during the iterations.

3.7 TSE-Complexity

Tononi, Sporns and Edelman introduced in 1994 in [53] another complexity measure and named it neural complexity C_N , but it is mostly referred to as TSE-complexity for Tononi-Sporns-Edelman-complexity. Although this measure does not fit entirely the method of defining complexity measures that was introduced up to this point, it is the measure that was proposed along with the framework that evolved into the setting of integrated information as mentioned in Section 3.6. This is the reason why a thesis about complexity and integrated information does not feel complete without discussing TSE-complexity.

The framework proposed in [53] analyzes the structure of groups of neurons by modeling them as stationary stochastic processes and uses the concept of mutual information to characterize the deviation from independence in subsets of increasing size.

To do this, one needs to generalize the concept of mutual information to more than two variables. This leads to the multi-information:

Definition 30 (Multi-Information). For a random vector $Z = (Z_1, \dots, Z_N)$, $I = \{1, \dots, N\}$, $N \in \mathbb{N}$ with the probability distribution $P \in \mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$ the multi-information is defined as

$$I(Z) := \sum_{i \in I} H_P(Z_i) - H_P(Z).$$

Using this concept, the TSE complexity is defined as

Definition 31 (TSE-Complexity). The TSE-complexity of a system consisting a random vector $Z = (Z_1, \dots, Z_N)$ is defined as

$$C_{TSE}(Z) := \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\frac{k}{N} I(Z) - I(k, N) \right)$$

with

$$I(k, N) := \binom{N}{k}^{-1} \sum_{\substack{J \subseteq I \\ |J|=k}} I(Z_J).$$

Therefore this measure is the sum over the differences between the multi-information of the whole system and the multi-information of weighted subsets of the system with increasing size. This results in a measure that is low for systems whose components are either totally dependent or independent and high for systems whose components show independence in small subsets and the dependence increases with the size of the subsets. This concept was defined in order to fit the structure of the brain, which is divided in groups of neurons with high interactions inside the group and a low dependency on neurons of other groups.

This measure belongs to a slightly different class of complexity measures. It is a special case of the weighted information distances described in [7] 6.1.3 or [38] .

4 Summary and next Steps

This thesis discusses different complexity measures arising in the context of integrated information. The integrated information theory developed in the last decades and therefore has still many open questions.

The theoretical foundations in Section 2 provide us with tools to examine and understand these measures. Information theory presents a probabilistic approach to the concept of information, most importantly entropy and KL-divergence. In information geometry this gets combined with differential geometry. This leads to a basic understanding of the structure of manifolds consisting of probability distribution. There we see why the KL-divergence is a natural choice for a notion of distance and we gain two important tools: the generalized Pythagorean theorem and the projection theorem.

Graphical models are a type of stochastic models that is very accessible, because of the representation of the respective Markov-properties in form of a graph. Conditional independence statements play an important role in analyzing the measure called integrated information and this yields a connection to algebraic statistics.

The measure belonging to mutual information is presented more as a means to define the second postulate than a serious complexity measure. Although too many connections get removed in this setting, it has the upside that it is straightforward to calculate. Additionally, it is easy to understand due to its disconnected distributions being a graphical model. Similarly, the sum of transfer entropies is a naturally occurring idea in this context. There we remove the interactions one at a time and take the sum over the resulting differences, hence it is a slightly different approach. A very easy example discussed in Section 3.7 shows that the sum of transfer entropies does not satisfy the second postulate.

The stochastic interaction has different positive properties. We are able to model the family of distributions belonging to the disconnected system as a graphical model which makes it more accessible. Additionally, it has an easy closed formula for the calculation of Φ . Despite that it has the problem of sometimes exceeding the mutual information.

Trying to fix this problem leads in two different directions, the geometric integrated information and the common exterior influence. While the geometric integrated information measure satisfies the second postulate and belongs also to a graphical model, it now fails the first. Additionally, it is not possible to calculate the value of this measure directly in general. We are able to resolve this issue by using an iterative scaling algorithm to gain the distribution belonging to the disconnected system.

The common exterior influence might be another way to resolve the problem of stochastic interaction. In this new approach we use the common exterior influence, whose existence was problematic in the case of stochastic interaction, in order to replace the edge between the Y_i 's. We saw that this type does satisfy Postulate 1 and that $M_{CEI} \not\subseteq M_{GI}$ as well as $M_{GI} \not\subseteq M_{CEI}$. The details of this model still need further investigations.

Another way to solve these problems is the integrated information measure. This satisfies both postulates, but it has no closed form representation in general. The distributions corresponding to the disconnected model also do not form a graphical model. Therefore this measure has to be calculated and analyzed with different tools. Two ways to do so were presented here, namely the primary decomposition of the corresponding conditional independence ideal and the introduction of a new divergence corresponding to the structure of the families of distributions belonging to the different conditional independence ideals. The latter combined with the new generalized Pythagorean theorem might lead to a better understanding of the structure of this model. Using the primary decomposition we see that even the smallest possible example, $n = 2$ and binary variables, does only decompose into a set of distributions on the boundary and one that encodes the conditional independence structure.

Surprisingly, the newly proposed generalized iterative scaling algorithm turns out to not necessarily converge towards the rI-projection, despite of the close conceptual relation to iterative scaling and the usage of rI-projections in each step. The small example in Section 3.6.1 is a case of such a situation where the actual Φ differs from the one calculated with the help of the new algorithm.

In the end we circle back to the beginning of the integrated information theory and present the TSE-complexity. This does not measure the integrated information in the same sense as the others, but it can be seen as a starting point of this research branch.

In conclusion, this thesis presents and analyzes different well known measures and describes some new approaches that might be worth exploring. These are the definition of the new measure using the common exterior influence and the tools developed to examine the structure of the manifolds corresponding to integrated information.

Symbols

$\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z})$	Set of probability distributions on the Markov-process $(\mathcal{X}_t)_{t \in \mathbb{N}}$.	7
$\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{Z}, \theta)$	Statistical model on \mathcal{Z} parameterized by θ .	15
$\mathcal{E}(G)$	Graphical model corresponding to a graph G .	32
$\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$	Functions from \mathcal{Z} to \mathbb{R} .	7
$\mathcal{E}(f, P^0)$	Exponential family with respect to the reference measure P^0 .	22
$M(\eta)$	Mixture family.	24
$\mathcal{P}^\circ(\mathcal{Z})$	Interior of the set of probability distributions on \mathcal{Z} .	16
$S(\mathcal{Z})$	Dual space of $\mathbb{R}^{\mathcal{Z}}$.	17
$D_{\mathfrak{y} \mathfrak{x}}(P \parallel Q)$	conditional KL-divergence between the distributions P and Q .	13
$I(X; Y)$	mutual Information of X and Y .	13
$X_{I \setminus \{i\}}$	Complement of X_i in X .	34
$\Phi(P)$	Complexity of a system described by the distribution P .	12
$(Z_t)_{t \in \mathbb{N}}$	Discrete n -dimensional Markov-process.	7
$D_{\mathfrak{x}}(P \parallel Q)$	KL-divergence between the probability distributions P and Q .	11
$E_P[f_i]$	The expectation value of f_i given the distribution P .	23
$H_P(X Y)$	Conditional entropy of $X Y$.	10
$H_P(X)$	Entropy of a random variable X .	10
$H_{P,Q}(X)$	Cross entropy of X .	11
$I(Z)$	The multi-information of random vector Z .	67
M_{CEI}	Disconnected system of common exterior influence.	51
M_G	Disconnected system of integrated information.	53
M_{GI}	Disconnected system of geometric integrated information.	48
M_I	Disconnected system of mutual information.	39
M_S	Disconnected system of stochastic interaction.	43
$M_{T_{ij}}$	One disconnected system belonging to transfer entropy.	42
$S(P)$	The support of the probability distribution P .	21
$im(\phi)$	The image of a function ϕ .	16

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